

D4.1: Systemic Innovation Maturity Gaps

Disclaimer and acknowledgements

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101036388

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Acronym	ZeroW	Grant Agreement No	101036388
Full Title	Systemic Innovations Towards a Zero Food Waste Supply Chain - ZeroW		
Call	H2020-LC-GD-2020 Building a low-carbon, climate resilient future: Research and innovation in support of the European Green Deal.		
Topic	LC-GD-6-1-2020	Type of action	IA
Project coordinator	Inlecom Commercial Pathways		
Project URL	http://www.zerow-project.eu/		
Deliverable	D4.1 Systemic Innovation maturity gaps		
Document Type	R	Dissemination Level	PU
Lead beneficiary	EV ILVO		
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Due date of delivery	30/06/2022	Submission date	30/06/2022

Document information

Document history			
Issue	Date	Comment	Author
V1.0	28/06/2022	Deliverable ready for submission	Isabeau Coopmans (ILVO)

Approved by:

Issue	Date	Name	Organisation
V1.0	28/06/2022	Quality review completed: Debolina Paul	DIGI

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Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Table 1 Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Acronym / Term	Description
EC	European Commission
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
F2F	Farm-to-Fork
FLW	Food Loss and Waste
GHG	Greenhouse gases
JRC	Joint Research Centre
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LRL	Legal Readiness Level
MRL	Marketing Readiness Level
ManuRL	Manufacturing Readiness Level
MarketRL	Market Readiness Level
ORL	Organisational Readiness Level
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SI	Systemic Innovation
SILL	Systemic Innovations Living Labs
SIP	Systemic Innovation Process
SIRL	Systemic Innovation Readiness Level
SRL	Societal Readiness Level
R4D	Research for Development

Executive summary

By delivering clarifications around three major Systemic Innovation (SI) maturity gaps, this deliverable aims to support the SILLs throughout the phases of their systemic innovation process. Chapter 1 clarifies the position of this deliverable in the ZeroW project. Chapter 2 introduces the need to address three particular SI maturity gaps. The three SI maturity gaps that were addressed for this deliverable are: (1) the need for a shared understanding of FLW definition; (2) the need for a shared and better understanding of the conflict mechanisms between FLW solutions and food poverty problem; and (3) the need for a tool that helps to achieve systemic innovation. Chapter 3 explains how FLW will be defined and interpreted in the ZeroW project. Chapter 4 sheds more light on how to understand the conflict mechanisms between FLW solutions and food poverty problems, and how to take such mechanisms into account when building FLW solutions. Chapter 5 provides a methodology that will help SILLs to (1) incorporate several innovation dimensions into their FLW solution building; and (2) monitor the systemic innovation readiness level of their FLW solution throughout the project.

1. The ZeroW project: background

1.1. ZeroW project summary

Figure 1: ZeroW at a glance

The ZeroW approach involves the following elements:

Figure 2: ZeroW approach

As Figure 1 and Figure 2 demonstrate, the SILLs can be seen as the core of the ZeroW project, since the **Systemic Innovations (SIs)** that are developed in the nine SILLs are central in the project's overall approach. Each SI is a concrete and holistic solution to a FLW problem. SIs address different innovation dimensions, meaning that different types of innovations, such as business and policy innovations, will be part of the FLW solutions. This implies that the nine ZeroW SILLs will illustrate how the ZeroW project uses a broader approach to FLW solutions than previous solutions that were usually largely technology-centred. Whereas maximizing resource efficiency may be important for reducing FLW through optimization of food harvesting, processing, and delivery processes, by considering conflict mechanisms at higher level, a systemic solution to FLW thinks further and tries to avoid possible 'collateral damages' that may result from a linear, non-systemic approach.

The process of this systemic solution building is called the **systemic innovation process (SIP)**. Each SILL will go through a SIP during the ZeroW project, hence when we talk about the **SILL processes**, we refer to the SIPs that happens in the SILLs. As showed in Figure 4, The SILL processes encompass the following (recurrent) phases: preparation, set-up, prototyping, testing, assessment, and demonstration. This process is not expected to be linear, rather to happen in an iterative way. The SIPs/SILL processes will likely be different in each SILL because the durations of each phase and the number of iterations may vary.

The SILLs strive for their SI solutions to be ready for full scale-up at the end of the ZeroW project, and to ultimately reach a large-scale usage by society. With this in mind, the SILLs will work intensively on the **SILL process** during the ZeroW project. As showed in Figure 4, In the ZeroW project the stages of the **SILL process** are organized in two main periods in time: the preparation and implementation period. The content of the present document is meant to support the SILLs in in one or more of those stages during both periods in time, by delivering clarifications around three major SI maturity gaps.

1.2. Situation of this deliverable in the ZeroW project

*To reach its goals, ZeroW is divided into 11 WPs with different goals, tasks and deliverables. The present deliverable is part of **WP4** (visualised in*

); which deals with the management and support of the SILL communities by providing them with various tools and practices conducive for their **SILL process**.

Figure 4 reveals how WP4 links to WPs 5, 6, and 7. One of the major aims of WP4 is to enable the SILLs to push the **SI readiness** of their FLW solution to an as high as possible state; in order to enlarge the changes of successful large-scale commercialisation and implementation beyond the timeline of the ZeroW project.

Figure 3: WP4 tasks, deliverables, objectives

This document contributes to the WP4 goals by addressing **three SI maturity gaps**, which is a precondition for SILLs to be able to build, test, and demonstrate their SIs:

- (1) the need to decide on a **FLW definition** that enables and supports the actions and intended impacts of the SILLs, in a comparable way;
- (2) the need to achieve a better understanding of inconsistencies between strategies addressing **FLW versus** strategies addressing **food poverty**;
- (3) the need to develop a **tool** that can be used **for steering the SI evolution and monitor the progress made** in the SILLs throughout the project.

Addressing these SI maturity gaps is one of the aspects required for reaching SI. A systemic FLW solution is a SI if it meets two conditions. The first condition is that the **SIP needs to be systemic**; meaning that multiple actors are involved in the SIP, building the FLW solution in a participatory way. The second condition is that the **FLW solution itself needs to be systemic**; meaning that the FLW solution addresses multiple innovation dimensions. Figure 4 **summarizes how the toolbox supports the SILLs in reaching such SI**: first, the toolbox provides them with useful existing tools, which are practical methods and techniques proven to help make FLW solution-thinking more systemic. These tools are presented in D4.2. Second, the

toolbox provides them with the **SIRL tool**, presented in chapter 5 of this deliverable, a tool specifically developed within ZeroW that helps SILLs to (1) include as many relevant innovation dimensions as needed into their FLW solution building, and (2) evaluate how ready their FLW solution is for scale-up, based on the maturity of each innovation dimension of their FLW solution.

Figure 4: Sill Toolbox and the Systemic Innovation Process

The SILL toolbox aims to support the ZeroW SILLs in managing and enhancing their systemic FLW solutions throughout the systemic innovation process (SIP). The toolbox consists of a set of selected existing tools (presented in D4.2); and the SIRL, a tool specifically designed in the ZeroW project to support the SILLs in monitoring the SI readiness of their solution (presented in this deliverable). The first version of the toolbox is made available to the SILLs in M6 of the ZeroW project via D4.1 and D4.2. It is important that afterwards, the SILLs start using the tools and provide feedback to ILVO, so that the toolbox can be updated where necessary during the ZeroW project. The use of the SIRL will be supervised actively in the context of WP5. The use of the other tools depends fully on SILLs' needs, hence SILLs must explore themselves which tools they want to use.

1.3. Mapping ZeroW outputs

Table 2 clarifies how the current document contributes to the ZeroW commitments, as formulated in the GA.

Table 2 Adherence to ZeroW Grant Agreement deliverable and work description

ZEROW GA Component Title	ZEROW GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
T4.1 Shared resources for Systemic Innovation	This Task will develop and manage the systemic innovation resources to be shared with the SILLs, to equip and familiarise/train the SILL members in embedding them in their ideation, prototyping, testing, demonstrating, scaling-up and commercialising activities. The shared resources will comprise of two groups of outputs. The first group of outputs are presented in this deliverable, the second group in D4.2. The first group of outputs will address specific innovation maturity gaps that are required for solution building, testing and demonstration in the ZeroW SILLs.	All	This deliverable provides shared resources to SILLs by addressing three SI maturity gaps.
T5.1 Methodology for assessing ZeroW systemic innovations	This task will further define the ZeroW methodology (as presented in the GA in section 1.3.2) in detail and will adapt it to the specific conditions of each SILL. The methodology will address three assessment views, and the present deliverable supports the first assessment view; which is the monitoring of the extent that the SILL innovations are improving during the project. This monitoring is done by use of the Systemic Innovation Readiness Level (SIRL) tool.	5	Chapter 5 of this deliverable presents the first version of the SIRL tool; to be used in WP5.
DELIVERABLE			
D4.1 Systemic Innovation maturity gaps	The specific innovation maturity gaps identified include the: (1) Development of a revised definition of FLW (building on the existing ones of FAO and FUSIONS), encompassing food losses in the whole food chain (including pre-harvest food losses) and providing also insight on their impact in terms of the resultant nutritional values lost and the corresponding GHG emissions incurred. The results will be used in SILL01 (F2F FLW monitoring & assessment); (2) Understanding of the conflict mechanisms between FLW reduction & food poverty. The results will be used in SILL07 (FLW reduction through efficient food bank networks); (3) Development of a Systemic Innovation Readiness Level, to be used by all SILLs.	All	Chapters 3, 4 and 5 deal with SI maturity gap 1, 2 and 3, respectively.

1.4. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

Chapter 2 explains the need to address three predetermined SI maturity gaps for ZeroW. Chapter 3 deals with the first maturity gap, which is the need to be very transparent on what **FLW definition** to be used in ZeroW. Chapter 4 deals with understanding **conflict mechanisms between solving FLW versus food poverty problems**, which must be considered when thinking systemically. The **Systemic Innovation Readiness Level (SIRL)**, presented in chapter 5, is ZeroW's main tool for assessing the readiness of the systemic innovations, that are demonstrated in the SILLs, to be implemented and commercialized at a higher level. In the context of WP5, it will be further used and – if necessary – adapted, based on the experiences of the SILLs.

By addressing the three SI maturity gaps, a first step is made towards achieving SI in the ZeroW SILLs.

2. Introduction: The need to address Systemic Innovation Maturity Gaps

FLW related problems, being complex and wicked problems, demand original and innovative solutions that are materialized as a systemic approach. A **systemic innovation (SI)** is a set of interdependent innovations which synergistically and dynamically interact; in a way that they minimise detrimental trade-offs while maximising the overall impact potential of the SI. This way, the different innovations actively interconnect important sub-entities of the system¹. Most importantly, systemic innovations are fundamentally new in the way the different innovations of the complete set relate to each other².

Former initiatives aiming to address FLW largely tended to lack attention for specific inconsistency issues regarding SI solution building. Concretely, three major **SI maturity gaps** that directly influence capacities to reduce FLW were identified:

- (1) A first SI maturity gap is about inconsistent usage of various FLW definitions. Furthermore, the consistent focus on volumetric assessments tends to limit the possibilities for devising systemic FLW solutions that take into account impacts that go beyond volume. A approach to the FLW definition and problem statement across the SILLs should be reached.

1 Davies, A., Mulgan, G., Norman, W., Pulford, L., Patrick, R., Simon, J., 2012. Systemic Innovation. Social Innovation Europe

2 Suurs, R. & Roelofs, E. (2014). Systemic Innovation: Concepts and tools for strengthening National and European eco-policies. TNO Report R10903.Delft.

- (2) A second SI maturity gap is linked to systems thinking and identifies trade-offs and synergies that arise at the interface of two wicked problems: reducing food waste versus eliminating food poverty. To put it concrete: addressing FLW problems in a systemic way may contradict efforts to tackle food poverty problems. Indeed, mechanisms driving the quest to move towards a zero food waste supply chain risk to conflict mechanisms driving the quest to move towards zero hunger and full food secure society. For systemic FLW solutions to be just, they need to be aware of trade-offs and synergies.
- (3) A third SI maturity gap deals with the need for a proper methodology for assessing the readiness of innovative systemic FLW solutions to be used at scale. While it is widely acknowledged that FLW is a wicked problem that demands *systemic* solution building³⁴, so far the focus of FLW solution building was largely unidimensional; often concentrated on developing a new technology application. However, for FLW solutions to achieve impact at scale, systemic approaches are needed that include a multitude of innovation dimensions, like business and policy innovations which allow implementation of a technological innovation in real environments.

To make sure that the ZeroW SILLs create innovative solutions that include the awareness of these SI maturity gaps, and to enable them to build effective FLW solution that take the above three issues into consideration, this document addresses these three SI maturity gaps in the following ways:

- (1) Proposing a **FLW definition** to be used throughout the ZeroW project. Additionally, SILL1 will work further on this.
- (2) Build a more clear and profound **understanding of the conflict mechanism(s) between FLW reduction and food poverty**. A transparent idea about the inconsistencies between the solutions for these two major challenges is needed to ensure a just transition towards a zero food waste supply chain, meaning that the positive and negative impacts from the innovative solutions are fairly balanced across affected food system stakeholders (including consumers).
- (3) The need for action-oriented tools that help monitoring and assessing the progress of SI solution-building processes in more proactive and anticipatory way (instead of a retrospective way)⁵ is addressed by the genesis of the **ZeroW**

3 Rittel, H. W. J., & Webber, M. M. (1973). Dilemmas in a general theory of planning. *Policy Sciences*, 4: 155–169.

4 Zivkovic, S. (2018). Systemic Innovation Labs: A Lab for Wicked Problems. *Social Enterprise Journal*, 14(3): 348-366.

5 Schut, M., Leeuwis, C., & Thiele, G. (2020). Science of Scaling: Understanding and guiding the scaling of

SIRL assessment tool. The initial version of is tool is presented in this deliverable. Throughout the course of the ZeroW project, this tool will be used by all SILLs (in the context of WP5) and this initial version will be updated if adaptations appear necessary based on feedback from the SILLs.

3. Defining Food Loss and Waste (FLW)

ZeroW SILLs will build, test and demonstrate systemic innovations in nine Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs). Each aim to contribute to ZeroW's overall and dual ambition: **to halve FLW by 2030 and ensure the enabling conditions for near-zero FLW by 2050.**

A **core demonstrative environment** will support and enable the SILLs with their innovation along the value chain, and help ensure their long term sustainability. This includes addressing specific innovation maturity gaps, including the need for an agreed definition of Food Loss and Waste. Indeed, a shared understanding of what food loss and waste is, as well as its impact - not just in terms of volume but also in terms of the resultant nutritional values lost and the corresponding GHG emissions incurred - will help the SILLs to act with more precision to introduce innovative systemic solutions for FLW and enable them to assess the impact of their solutions in a comparable way.

Our ambition for this part of D4.1 is therefore to advance one definition of FLW for use within the work of the SILLs, and to provide guidance on its use in practice by SILLs.

3.1. Definitions of food loss and waste

Different definitions for food loss and waste exist. This part discusses the EU and FAO definitions as well as the definition proposed by the FUSIONS project.

3.1.1 FUSIONS definition

FUSIONS⁶ (Food Use for Social Innovation by Optimising Waste Prevention Strategies) was an EU research and innovation project that was funded under the 7th Framework Programme for Research of the European Union that ran from

innovation for societal outcomes. Agricultural Systems, 184, 102908. doi:10.1016/j.agsy.2020.102908

⁶ <https://www.eu-fusions.org/index.php/about-fusions> and <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/311972>

August 2012 to July 2016. It aimed at reducing food waste, and played a pivotal role in deepening the definition of food waste. It also provided one of the first estimates of FLW in the EU, thereby indicating that around 88 million tonnes of food waste were generated annually (an estimated 20% of the total food produced) with associated costs estimated at 143 billion euros (FUSIONS, 2016).

FUSIONS **defines** food waste as follows:

“**Food waste** is any food, and inedible parts of food, removed from the food supply chain to be recovered or disposed (including composted, crops ploughed in/not harvested, anaerobic digestion, bio-energy production, co-generation, incineration, disposal to sewer, landfill or discarded to sea).”

FUSIONS considers **inedible parts** of food as food waste⁷. Inedible parts of food are those parts that are not intended for human consumption, such as bones, rinds, and pits/stones. Hence, food waste includes parts of food intended to be eaten and parts of food not intended to be eaten⁸. However, there is no universal definition of the inedible fraction of food waste, which is influenced by a range of variables, including cultural habits (e.g. chicken feet are more commonly consumed in some countries than in others), socio-economic factors, food availability and price, technological advances, international trade, and geography. This definition is clarified with the **theoretical framework** of FUSIONS (see Figure 5).

⁷ <https://www.eu-fusions.org/index.php/about-food-waste/280-food-waste-definition>

⁸ [EUR-Lex - 32008L0098 - EN - EUR-Lex \(europa.eu\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/lexuri-uri.do?uri=CELEX_32008L0098)

Figure 5: Theoretical framework of FUSIONS (source: <https://www.eu-fusions.org/index.php/about-food-waste/280-food-waste-definition>)

According to FUSIONS, food waste **does not include**:

- pre-harvest losses, i.e. losses that occur before the raw material is ready for harvest or slaughter, such as weather-related damage to crops (which is accounted for as agricultural waste);
- Food and inedible parts removed from the food supply chain but valorised as animal feed;
- by-products, i.e. edible or inedible material resulting from food production and processing, such as peels, bones, and scrapings, that are then used for non-food purposes (e.g. cosmetics, glue, petfood);
- food packaging, such as boxes, wrapping, or plastic containers (although edible packaging would be considered food because it is intended for human consumption).

Drink and liquid waste, fish discarded to sea and waste of any materials that are ready for harvest, but which are not harvested, **are included** in FUSIONS's definition of food waste, making its perimeter wider and broader than other definitions.

3.1.2 EU definition

The EU embedded a definition of FLW in its legislation. Several main pieces of legislation make up the EU definition of **Food Waste**. The definition is provided in the amendment to **Directive 2008/98/EC** on Waste⁹. In this document, **food waste** is defined as¹⁰:

“All food as defined in Article 2 of Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 of the European Parliament and of the Council (a.k.a. **EU General Food Law**) that has become waste. The definition of 'food' laid down in Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 encompasses food as a whole, along the entire food supply chain from production until consumption. Food also includes inedible parts, where those were not separated from the edible parts when the food was produced, such as bones attached to meat destined for human consumption. Hence, food waste can comprise items that include parts of food intended to be ingested and parts of food not intended to be ingested. 'Waste' means any substance or object which the holder discards or intends or is required to discard” (European Parliament and Council, 2008).

⁹ EUR-Lex - 32008L0098 - EN - EUR-Lex (europa.eu)

¹⁰ Caldeira, C., De Laurentiis, V., Sala, S. Suggestions to improve data coverage and comparability in food waste accounting studies across the EU, EUR 30024 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2019, ISBN 978-92-76-14272-0, doi:10.2760/850030, JRC118985

The EC definition is **in line with the one reported in FUSIONS**. However, the EU definition of food waste does not include losses at stages of the food supply chain where certain products have not yet become food as defined in Article 2 of Regulation (EC) No 178/2002, such as edible plants, which have not been harvested, excluding crops ploughed in/not harvested which are instead included in the FUSIONS definition. Therefore, although the EU definition recognizes the role played by primary production in creating FLW, **it disregards harvest FLW** (ie. Food left in the fields during or after harvest) and focuses on post-harvest FLW.

EUROSTAT’s Guidance on Food Waste (July 2021), which describes in detail the reporting of data on food waste and food waste prevention required from EU Member States, explains this in more detail by stating that *material lost in primary production (pre-harvest losses, losses at harvest, animals dead before slaughter) is not regarded as food waste, as it has not been regarded as “food” yet*.

An overall visual comparison between the FUSIONS and EU definition is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Comparison of FUSIONS and EU definition of food waste (JRC, 2020)

Ongoing EC policy discussions around legislative proposals (e.g. amendments to the Waste Directive) could impact the EC legislative definition in the future.

3.1.3 FAO definition

In its 2019 State of Food and Agriculture report on Food Loss and Waste reduction¹¹, the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations defines both Food Loss and Food Waste:

“Food loss is the decrease in the quantity or quality of food resulting from decisions and actions by food suppliers in the chain, excluding retailers, food service providers and consumers¹². Empirically, it refers to any food that is **discarded, incinerated or otherwise disposed** of along the food supply chain from harvest/slaughter/catch up to, but excluding, the retail level, and **does not re-enter** in any other productive utilization, such as feed or seed.”¹³

By contrast, **“food waste** refers to the decrease in the quantity or quality of food resulting from decisions and actions by retailers, food service providers and consumers¹². Less food loss and waste would lead to more efficient land use and better water resource management with positive impacts on climate change and livelihoods.”¹⁴

This definition, while quite broad, differentiates between food loss and food waste. It serves as the basis for monitoring SDG 12.3-targets (Food Loss Index and Food Waste Index)¹⁵.

3.1.4 Which definition to use and related methodological aspects

SILLs need to be able to **assess and measure FLW, its impact and the impact of their interventions** in a **comparable** way. Measurements need to be comparable between SILLs, and beyond ZEROW. In addition, although FLW is a global challenge, assessments and measurements by SILLs need to be (in particular) relevant to the EU and EU Member State context.

In 2019 the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission (EC-JRC) published a **review of food waste quantification** in the Member States¹⁶. In this review EC-JRC pointed at the need for improved comparability of the results of different studies on

¹¹ <https://www.fao.org/3/ca6030en/ca6030en.pdf>, pp.4-6.

¹² The State of Food and Agriculture 2019 | FAO | Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations

¹³ <https://www.fao.org/platform-food-loss-waste/food-loss/introduction/en/>

¹⁴ <https://www.fao.org/platform-food-loss-waste/food-waste/introduction/en/>

¹⁵ <https://www.fao.org/sustainable-development-goals/indicators/1231/en/>

¹⁶ Caldeira, C., De Laurentiis, V., Sala, S. Suggestions to improve data coverage and comparability in food waste accounting studies across the EU, EUR 30024 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2019, ISBN 978-92-76-14272-0, doi:10.2760/850030, JRC118985

FLW. It indicated several methodological aspects that constrain the comparability and made a number of suggestions for improvement, including a **plea to choose the EU definition of food waste** as the base for studies.

The methodological aspects raised in this review and several of the suggestions made are also of high relevance to the practical work of the SILLs and the comparability of their actions and impact. Therefore, SILLs should follow the guidelines of this review with regards to (at least) the following 2 methodological aspects.

Which **definition** of FLW to use?

- To ensure the comparability of future food waste solutions, SILLs should use the EU definition of food waste, as provided in the amendment to Directive 2008/98/EC on Waste.
- This should also allow the SILLs to better clarify to what extent they can contribute to the reduction targets (to be defined in future EU legislation) within the context of the EU and its Member States.

How to account for **edible and inedible parts** when assessing FLW?

- In Delegated Decision 2019/1597, which deals with a common methodology and minimum quality requirements for the uniform measurement of levels of food waste, both the edible and inedible parts are quantified as food waste. Member States can, on a voluntary base, provide a breakdown between edible and inedible streams, in which they clearly identify what is accounted as edible and inedible parts.
- SILLs should follow the same approach.

In addition, the SILLs should – where possible - **comply with the following suggestions** derived from the EC-JRC review:

1. They should provide clear identification of the **geographical scope** of their measurements (e.g. Member State, NUTS region), and of the **timeframe** that is used (e.g. full calendar year);
2. They should indicate the **stages of the food supply chain** that have been included in the assessment. Article 1 of Delegated Act 2019/1597 states that “the amounts of food waste shall be measured separately for the following stages of the food supply chain: (a) primary production; (b) processing and manufacturing; (c) retail and other distribution of food; (d) restaurants and food services; (e) households.” If a **more granular view** is used (focussing on

part(s) of the stages) then the SILLs should document how these parts relate to the 5 stages;

3. SILLs should be aware that it has been hard to quantify the food waste stream that is discharged to the sewer or to wastewater treatment. WRAP has issued a specific guideline related to this issue (see [Quantifying food waste in effluent | WRAP](#));
4. The **most accurate methods** should be considered or used in the quantification of food waste: direct methods (quantifying directly the amount of food waste by: weighing, waste composition analysis (WCA), surveys, diaries, records, and observation) and/or indirect methods (where food waste is estimated from various secondary data sources: modelling, mass balance, proxy data, and literature data). SILLs should be aware of the FLW Protocol's Guidance on FLW quantification methods and of the methods outlined in delegated Decision 2019/1597 (annex III and annex IV). More than one method can be used to improve the robustness of the measurement.
5. SILLs should base their quantification of food waste as much as possible on **primary data** to contribute to a more accurate and reliable picture of food waste generation. They should also report clearly which sampling and upscaling procedures were adopted. The FLW Protocol as well as the FUSIONS quantification manual provides guidance.
6. SILLs should provide a qualitative or quantitative assessment of **uncertainty** of the reported results.

This approach to the definition and measurement of FLW in ZEROW enables a practical and “actionable” way forward that limits possible innovation gaps linked to the FLW definition, and that supports the targeted systemic innovations.

3.2 Harvest and pre-harvest losses

As previously said, the EU definition of FLW does not include pre-harvest losses or harvest losses. However, this should not impede SILLs to assess and measure either harvest losses, or even pre-harvest losses, in practice. Below are some elements that can inform SILLs in their efforts to assess and measure harvest losses and to a lesser extent to measure pre-harvest losses.

FUSIONS and FAO describe harvest losses and pre-harvest losses as separate items.

FUSIONS considers as pre-harvest losses, losses that occur before the raw material is ready for harvest or slaughter. Harvest losses are described as food that is ready for harvest or slaughter, but that is lost. FUSIONS' “Food waste quantification

Manual¹⁷ includes a section on the recommended approach for assessing food waste in primary Production (agriculture, aquaculture, and fisheries).

In its methodology for monitoring SDG target 12.3 on FLW (and in particular for monitoring target SDG 12.3.1a; Food Loss Index) **FAO** describes both harvest and pre-harvest losses by stage and by commodity group (grains, fruits and vegetables, milk and meat, fish). For examples in the case of grains:

- Pre-harvest losses: Losses that occur before the beginning of the harvesting process and that may be due to attacks by insects, mites, rodents, birds, weeds, or diseases afflicting and damaging crops.
- Harvest losses: These occur during the harvesting process and may be due to shattering, mechanical damage and shedding of the grain from the ears to the ground.

Also, Figure 7 clarifies the scope of SDG 12.3.1 and SDG 12.3.2. This figure also clarifies that FL due to extreme weather conditions is covered (in economic terms) separately by the SDG reporting of indicator SDG 1.5.

Figure 7: from PPT by FAO (EU Meeting on Food Loss Measurement Experiences and recommendations for quantifying food losses and waste from primary production; see [fw eu-plattform 20190201 sub-fwm pres-1.pdf \(europa.eu\)](https://eu-plattform.eu/2019/02/01/sub-fwm-pres-1.pdf))

As for the **FLW Protocol**, and for the purpose of the FLW Standard, “pre-harvest” refers to the stage in food production that occurs before a raw material for food is

¹⁷ <https://www.eu-fusions.org/phocadownload/Publications/FUSIONS%20Food%20Waste%20Quantification%20Manual.pdf>

ready for harvest or slaughter. The FLW Standard (Version 1.0) does not include provisions for how to quantify losses that occur pre-harvest. The FLW Standard also states that pre-harvest losses are different from losses that occur at harvest or later, both in terms of how they are manifested and how they are quantified. Several of the methods discussed in the FLW Protocol's "Guidance on FLW Quantification Methods"¹⁸ can be used for assessing harvest losses.

3.3 Going beyond volume to measure impact of food loss and waste

It is necessary and useful to express FLW in terms or units of measurement that **go beyond weight or volume**. It is **necessary** because it can help to identify those FLW actions, pathways and solutions based not just on the volume reduction of FLW, but also, and even more so, on the impact that they have on food and nutritional security, on climate change mitigation, on use of natural resources, land and water, on biodiversity, on environmental pressure, on economic and societal aspects and costs. It is **useful** because the expression of FLW in terms of impact can help the wider public to assess the seriousness of FLW and to emphasize the opportunities and added value that systemic solutions for FLW hold.

As indicated by the FAO's global **Food Waste Footprint (FWF)**¹⁹ food waste represents a missed opportunity to improve food security and comes at a steep environmental price. The financial costs of food waste it identified amount to about USD 1 trillion each year. Their 2013 publication also quantified the impacts of FLW on the atmosphere, water, land and biodiversity, using an LCA model and identified 'hotspots' (for regions, commodities and stages of the food supply chain) where mitigation efforts should focus. The 2015 update of the FWF project translated the environmental impacts of food waste into societal costs, measured in monetary terms. It used a full-cost accounting (FCA) methodology to evaluate the direct financial costs, the lost value of ecosystems goods and services, and the loss of well-being associated with natural resource degradation. It concluded that the global full costs of food waste amount to about 2.6 trillion USD per year, including USD 700 billion of environmental costs and USD 900 billion of social costs.

More recently in 2022, the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission (EC-JRC) published another global assessment of the impact of FLW reduction over time

¹⁸ https://flwprotocol.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/05/FLW_Protocol_Guidance_on_FLW_Quantification_Methods.pdf

¹⁹ <https://www.fao.org/nr/sustainability/food-loss-and-waste/en/>

on the sustainability of food systems²⁰. Figure 8 is taken from this study and shows the impact of different FLW reduction scenarios for the EU on the 3 dimensions of sustainability.

Overview of scenario impacts on food system objectives and indicators for the EU

Sustainable Food System objectives - EU		Related SDGs	FL (-50%)	FW (-50%)	FWL comb.	FWL & Costs	FWL & Energy price	FWL & Diets
Social <i>End hunger and achieve healthy diets for all</i>	Improved diets							
	Cheaper food							
	More ag jobs							
Environment <i>Sustainable use of biodiversity and natural resources</i>	Reduced land use							
	Less emissions							
	Reduced water use							
Economy <i>Eliminate poverty and increase income and wealth</i>	Economic growth							
	Agri sector growth							
	Higher producer prices							
Important remarks:		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Indicators in bold are those relevant for the whole society and not a specific sector. Coloured circles indicate the direction towards reaching an objective. The expected reduced productivity due to environmental oriented policies in the Farm to Fork strategy could be counterbalanced with the increased efficiency as shown in the FWL scenario. Consequently, the impacts on the agricultural sector would look differently. Not creating more agricultural jobs while producing more, means a higher labour productivity. The reduced use of natural resources improves biodiversity and thus creates additional (socioeconomic) values. General health benefits through a better diet and better environment create enormous socioeconomic benefits, not included in this study. 						
		Scenarios: FL (-50%): Food loss reduction by 50% FW (-50%): Food waste reduction by 50% FWL comb.: Food loss and waste reduction combined FWL & Costs: as FWL with 5% costs for reduction FWL & Energy price: as FWL with a 25% higher oil price FWL & Diets: as FWL with a healthier diet (EAT-Lancet)						
Source: MAGNET model, transformation of results into more qualitative statements.								

Figure 8: Overview of scenario impacts on food system objectives and indicators for the EU (source: Boysen-Urban et al. (2022))

This multiple indicator perspective along the lines of selected SDGs objectives is interesting because it shows that a multitude of synergies and trade-offs can be identified, for example between reducing GHG-emissions and producer prices, and that actions, pathways and solutions will need to consider these synergies and trade-offs, also within ZEROW.

As indicated above, FAO provided methodologies to assess the impact of FLW. In addition to them, the FLW Protocol also provided **technical guidance in their FLW Standard**²¹. Appendix D of that document provides an introductory overview to expressing FLW in terms of environmental impacts, nutritional content or financial implications. It provides technical considerations, examples and resources to help

²⁰ Boysen-Urban, K., M`barek, R., Philippidis, G. and Ferrer, H., Exploring changing food attitudes to respect planetary boundaries, EUR 30794 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2022, ISBN 978-92-76-40788-1, doi:10.2760/744504, JRC126157.

²¹ https://flwprotocol.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/FLW_Standard_final_2016.pdf

with the conversion factors, while also indicating that conversions from volume to other units generally bring along additional assumptions and therefore will impact the level of uncertainty of the reported data. It also highlights that different conversion factors might need to be combined and that conversion factors and units can be chosen for specific purposes and particular situations.

- With regards to the environmental impact the FLW Standard highlights that when FLW is reduced the embedded resource use (land, water, energy and GHG) is optimised. It refers to the FAO's Food Wastage Footprint (published in 2013, updated in 2015) for methods on assessing the environmental impacts of FLW.
- It explains that FLW also represents a loss of nutrients, which includes carbohydrates, proteins, fat, vitamins and minerals. For that reason it is also interesting to indicate the nutritional content (of the edible part of FLW) that is lost, expresses as nutrients, energy, or in some situations as meals or portions.
- Finally it adds that FLW also incurs direct costs and foregone benefits along the supply chain. Costs to society can also be assigned to account for environmental externalities.

Finally, here are two additional remarks that do not relate directly to the measurement of the impact of FLW, but that are important to mention because of their close thematic connection to the topic of this point:

- The amount of FLW that is reported can be reduced by selecting specific solutions and **strategies for re-use, recycling, recovery or disposal** of FLW. It is important to state that for the different FLW streams different reuse or recycling actions will have a different impact, and that this fact should also be taking into account;
- Actions that tackle **overconsumption** in food systems show clear synergies with the objectives of reducing FLW (e.g. contribute to the reduction of resource/water/land use, to GHG-emission reduction).

4. Conflict mechanisms between FLW reduction and food poverty

4.1 Food security, food poverty and healthy diets

Food security is a widely acknowledged as a global challenge. It is addressed by one of the Sustainable Development Goals in the UN's Agenda 2030, in particular by SDG 2. This SDG Goal has been named "Zero Hunger", and seeks to "end hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture."²² It is interconnected with several of the other 16 SDG Goals, which together set a target for overall social, economic, and environmental sustainability by 2030. The link with SDG 3 "Good Health and Wellbeing" in particular is important.

The SDG of Zero Hunger by 2030 consists of five individual subgoals, of which the first 2 subgoals specifically address food security and nutritional health (through nutritious food or healthy diets):

- Goal 2.1: By 2030, end hunger and ensure access by all people, in particular the poor and people in vulnerable situations, including infants, to **safe, nutritious, and sufficient food** all year round.
- Goal 2.2: By 2030, end all forms of **malnutrition**, including achieving, by 2025, the internationally agreed targets on stunting and wasting in children under 5 years of age, and address the nutritional needs of adolescent girls, pregnant and lactating women, and older persons.
- Goal 2.3: By 2030, double the **agricultural productivity** and **incomes** of small-scale food producers, in particular women, indigenous peoples, family farmers, pastoralists, and fishers, including through secure and equal access to land, other productive resources and inputs, knowledge, financial services, markets and opportunities for value addition and non-farm employment.
- Goal 2.4: By 2030, ensure **sustainable food production systems** and implement **resilient agricultural practices** that increase productivity and production, that help maintain ecosystems, that strengthen capacity for adaptation to climate change, extreme weather, drought, flooding, and other disasters and that progressively improve land and soil quality.
- Goal 2.5: By 2020, maintain the **genetic diversity** of seeds, cultivated plants, and farmed and domesticated animals and their related wild species, including through soundly managed and diversified seed and plant banks at the national, regional, and international levels, and promote access to and

²² [THE 17 GOALS | Sustainable Development \(un.org\)](https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/)

fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from the utilization of genetic resources and associated traditional knowledge, as internationally agreed.

However, despite these ambitions it is clear that **global food security is deteriorating**, partly through crises like Covid-19. Figure 9 shows that between 720 and 811 million people in the world were projected to face hunger in 2020. They are considered food insecure, which means that **they cannot rely on having a decent meal every day and regularly go to bed hungry**²³. Considering the middle of the projected range (768 million), around 118 million more people were facing hunger in 2020 than in 2019 – or as many as 161 million more, considering the upper bound of the projected range.

Figure 9: Food insecurity trend²³

Access to food is a challenge for even more people. Nearly one in three people in the world do not have access to adequate food. Finally, it is important to mention that also “nutritional security” remains a concern because for about 3 billion people the costs of a **healthy diet** were out of reach²⁴. All these numbers risk rising further

²³ [Hunger | FAO | Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations](#)

²⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/food-farming-fisheries/key_policies/documents/safeguarding-food-security-reinforcing-resilience-food-systems.pdf

due to Ukraine crisis and food price inflation and therewith falling further short of reaching the Sustainable Development Goals by 2030²⁵.

Within the EU a different picture emerges. According to the EC¹⁹, food availability is not at stake, though **food affordability** for low-income persons is. A fact which is likely to have impact on nutritional health and wellbeing. In 2020, **8.6% of the EU population** (an estimated 38 million people out of a total population of 448 million) and more than one in five people at risk of poverty (21.7%) were **unable to afford a meal with meat, fish or a vegetarian equivalent every second day**²⁶. This is one of thirteen items used to determine the severe material and social deprivation rate. These figures (EUROSTAT) show that **“food poverty”** in the EU is an issue. Recent reports show that also within the EU this problem has been and is increasing, due to the Covid 19 (30% increased demand to food banks during Covid-19 in 2020, according to FEBA), and due to price inflation for food and other major household expenses like energy and heating²⁷. EU funds such as the Fund for European Aid to the Most Deprived (FEAD) which support EU countries' actions to provide food and/or basic material assistance to the most deprived in the EU, are estimated to reach over 15 million people with food aid.

Research by Penne et al. compared the cost of an adequate (healthy) diet directly with disposable income to get a measure of the affordability problems for accessing a healthy diet. Their findings, that in 16 out of 24 countries at least 10 per cent of the population in (sub)urban areas risks have no access to a healthy diet due to insufficient income, emphasize the impact not just on EU food security but also on **EU nutritional health**²⁸.

4.2 FLW reduction and food security: conflicts, synergies and trade-offs

It is widely acknowledged that the **world can feed 10 billion people by 2050** and provide food and nutrition security while reducing emissions, curbing deforestation and alleviating poverty. However, it is also clear that the achievement of such a sustainable food system -that can deliver healthy diets for a growing population against the background of climate change and within planetary boundaries -

²⁵ <https://www.eu-fusions.org/index.php/about-fusions> and <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/311972>

²⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/-/ddn-20220225-1>

²⁷ Vlietstra, C. (2020) Voedselbanken in coronatijd: vraag stijgt, voedselaanbod daalt [Food banks in COVID times: demand rises, food supply decreases]. Vakblad Fondsenwerving, 22(7), December 2020 (in Dutch).

²⁸ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306919220301822>

presents **formidable challenges**²⁹. To tackle these challenges a wide range of actions will be needed that address consumption (e.g. shift to healthy diets) and production (e.g. improved production practices).

The **reduction of food losses and waste** -*a third of food biomass does not find its way to human consumption*- is seen as **one of the more important actions**, and has broad support from science, societal actors and policy makers. There are good reasons for that. Reducing FLW limits the amounts of resources, land and water that are lost, avoids costs related to labor, packaging or to the disposal of FLW, and increases the productivity of agriculture and food systems, at least with regards to material resource use. It also decreases environmental pressure and avoids GHG-emissions (FAO famously stated that food wastage ranks as the third largest source of emissions after the national emissions of the United States and China). Because of all these reasons, FLW reduction has the potential to **support food security** (in particular the availability of food) and help **the transition to sustainable food systems**. The reduction of FLW also is needed from an ethical point of view. Ethically it is necessary to address the obvious tensions between the millions of people that are food insecure, the fact that 30% of food is lost or wasted, or even the high prevalence of overconsumption in some parts of the world.

The detailed mechanisms through which the reduction of food losses and waste creates impact on access to (healthy) food and affordability of food (and therefore also on food security and food poverty) are less straight forward. Quantitative research under the JRC study “Exploring changing food attitudes to respect planetary boundaries”³⁰, which uses the FAO definition of food loss and food waste, shows the **complexity of these impact mechanisms**, and highlights that the reduction of food loss and of food waste each have different impacts on food quantities supplied and demanded, and on other the social, economic and environmental aspects of food systems, including price:

Model results revealed that food loss related to the production site leads to an increase in the quantity of agricultural and food commodities, which reduces market prices and, as a result, reduces input costs for food processing and thus boosts demand for now cheaper agricultural and food commodities. Furthermore, the study shows that reducing consumer food waste, as well as waste related to food

²⁹ Caldeira, C., De Laurentiis, V., Sala, S. Suggestions to improve data coverage and comparability in food waste accounting studies across the EU, EUR 30024 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2019, ISBN 978-92-76-14272-0, doi:10.2760/850030, JRC118985

³⁰ Boysen-Urban, K., M`barek, R., Philippidis, G. and Ferrer, H., Exploring changing food attitudes to respect planetary boundaries, EUR 30794 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2022, ISBN 978-92-76-40788-1, doi:10.2760/744504, JRC126157.

services and retail, subsequently counteracts these effects. Household food expenditure for certain products is now reduced; however, the rule on market prices that equalise supply and demand apply so that food waste and loss reductions taking place at the same time could result in increased food consumption as food, in general, becomes cheaper.

By showing that different FLW reduction strategies have different effects on food prices and quantities (some FLW reduction strategies increase prices) this study confirms the complex link with affordability of food (and food poverty). It does this without considering the added complexity that a change of food prices could also have an **additional negative or positive feedback** on the amount of food wasted. The situation is further complicated by the fact that lack of access to (healthy) food and low affordability of food, does not only depend on the price of food but also on items that fall **outside of the boundaries of food systems**, such as policies related to welfare and vulnerable groups, the affordability of other essential goods and services like energy and housing, or the design of the spatial environment.

These insights provide a good basis and argument for **a more comprehensive and systemic view on the mechanisms** that occur between different types of FLW reduction, food poverty and food security, and on **emerging trade-offs, conflicts and synergies**. Efforts to do this also need to acknowledge the importance of links to other systems (e.g. welfare system, housing system) that have an impact on affordability of and access to food. They also need to take into account that the trade-offs, conflicts and synergies can be different between countries that focus their attention on food loss and efficiency gains in the food supply chain, versus other countries that focus more on food waste reduction by retail, consumers and foodservice.

4.3 Food banks and redistribution of FLW

Many **interventions** are possible to reduce FLW. Figure 10 provides an overview. These interventions will be extended through initiatives of the Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs) in the ZEROW project.

Type	Sub-type
Redistribution	Surplus food redistribution
	Gleaning
	Digital tools for redistribution
Food valorisation	Value added processing
	Animal feed
Consumers behaviour change	Awareness/educational campaign
	Digital tool for behaviour change
	School programs
	Awards
Supply chain efficiency	Process innovation
	Innovation of products - packaging
	Innovation of products - date marking
	Training & guidelines
	Price discount
	Imperfect product sale
	Certification
	Public procurement
	Digital tools for supply chain efficiency
	Voluntary agreement
Food waste prevention governance	Regulatory framework/policy
	National food waste prevention program
	Fiscal incentives

Figure 10: Food waste reduction interventions (Source: Caldeira et al. 2019)³¹

Food redistribution interventions rank high in the broadly accepted **waste hierarchy** which is also central to the EU’s Waste Framework Directive. The **principles** behind this hierarchy are: that preventing waste is the preferred option; that sending waste to landfill should be the last resort; that reuse (food, feed) is preferred over recycling and recovery (for nutrients, energy). Obviously, there is also a clear synergy between SDG 2 “End Hunger” and FLW redistribution.

Food redistribution keeps FLW that would otherwise be lost in the food supply chain and uses it to provide food to people in need. Matching it with demand from these groups is more than getting the right **quantities** to the right people. It also requires fulfilling the need for **healthy (and safe) diets** and taking into account **consumer preferences**, for example in terms of convenience. This often translates in complex operations and logistics, in collaboration with food banks, to be able to identify FLW sources, and to bring them in a suitable format and in the right quantities to the places of demand.

³¹ Caldeira, C., V. De Laurentiis, S. Corrado, F. van Holsteyn, S. Sala (2019) Quantification of food waste per product group along the food supply chain in the European Union: a mass flow analysis. Resources, Conservation and Recycling 149: 479-488.

Figure 11: Waste hierarchy according to EU Waste Framework Directive 2008/98/EC (European Commission)

For addressing the SI maturity gap about the conflict mechanisms between FLW solutions and food poverty, more should be done to **reinforce food redistribution**. Further strengthening of the position of food banks is needed as they directly transform potential FLW into meals for food insecure citizens. Food waste reduction through efficient food bank networks is addressed in SILL7³². But much can still be done. Solutions that apply a form of price discrimination at the retail could be developed, for example by providing discounts on products that are close to their best-before-date only to food insecure people. Further work can be done on how we can increase the capacity of FLW redistribution to deliver healthy diets. After all, people in hunger do not care about weight of food, but about nutrients. So solutions are needed to allow us to valorize high-nutrient foods as much as possible. Furthermore, a concrete example from SILL 5 of ZEROW is to harvest vegetables with peculiarities (for example tomatoes) and use them in processed foods that are made available to those in need. Finally, it would be interesting to compare the combined FLW and hunger statistics among European countries to better understand differences and best practices in policies.

These are only a few examples of how FLW redistribution can further improve the livelihoods of people in food insecure situations. It is an important challenge for the remainder of the ZEROW project, and for the broad food research community, to come up with additional ideas for this and test them in practice.

³² #7 Food bank network (zerow-project.eu)

At the same time, we will have to be aware that the continued reduction of FLW (towards Zero Waste in 2050) will on the longer term have a strong impact on the current operating model of food banks, which relies heavily on FLW redistribution. **New strategies and operating models** will eventually be needed to provide food for food insecure citizens in the EU and beyond.

5. Monitoring systemic innovation using the SIRC tool

5.1. Systemic innovations encompass multiple dimensions

5.1.1. Theoretical background

When people hear the word *innovation*, they probably link this to a new product or technology. However, there are much more **types of innovations** that happen in various types of **dimensions**. Two examples in the field of FLW solutions are: a new food waste management scheme as a *governance innovation*; and the establishment of shifted social norms with regard to FLW as a *socio-cultural innovation*. Innovation should thus be interpreted very broadly as any new idea or any adaptation to an existing system that eventually materializes into added value if it is being applied in practice. **Multiple ways of classifying innovations into different dimensions** are possible. For example, socio-economic innovations can be considered a higher order innovation dimension that can be subdivided into the following sub-dimensions: organizational, physical material, service, and marketing innovations³³. In section 5.1.3, **we propose a way of classifying innovations that suits the FLW solutions that are developed in the SILLs**. In what follows, we argue **why it is important to consider different innovation dimensions** when ideating, developing, and scaling systemic solutions for complex problems.

Though innovations can relate to various dimensions, there currently exists a technocentric emphasis when it comes to assessing the readiness of innovative solutions to be implemented at larger scale³⁴. By way of contrast, it should be noticed that sometimes **non-technological innovations** are much more impactful than technological innovations. For example, a process of *cultural innovation* induced major societal changes in many Eastern European countries during the

³³ Johannessen, J., (2013). Innovation: a systemic perspective – developing a systemic innovation theory. *Kybernetes* 42, 1195–1217. <https://doi.org/10.1108/K-04-2013-0069>

³⁴ McCampbell, M., Adewopo, J., Klerkx, L., & Leeuwis, C. (2021). Are farmers ready to use phone-based digital tools for agronomic advice? Ex-ante user readiness assessment using the case of Rwandan banana farmers. *Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*, ahead-of-print (ahead-of-print): 1–23. doi:10.1080/1389224X.2021.1984955

1990s because the Fall of Communism allowed an “opening up” to influences of the West²⁴. Another example of a non-technological innovation with major societal consequences is the Club of Rome, which can be understood as an *institutional innovation* that induced a series of actions to address the global challenges of today³⁵. These examples illustrate that non-technological innovations can largely impact economy and society or can even be crucial for economic growth³⁶. Vice versa, economic/business innovations can accelerate institutional, socio-cultural, or even governance change. For example, intellectual property rights (*policy innovation*) and the emergence of joint stock companies (*business innovation*) both played a major role in the investment behaviour of capital holders (*behavioural innovation*) and R&D companies, and even in trade (*governance innovation*)³⁷. Thus, innovations are not solely important drivers for increased efficiency and productivity, but also for e.g. improved prosperity, justice, and well-being.

Beside the need to move away from the implicit assumption that technological innovation is always the starting point of innovative solutions, it is important to acknowledge that **successful innovative solutions encompass multiple dimensions at once**; such as changes in business organisations and strategies, acknowledging ethical and societal considerations, adapting regulatory frameworks. Indeed, many successful innovative solutions (i.e., solutions that achieved some kind of impact at scale) only became successful after having realized changes in multiple dimensions, such as the legal, cultural and institutional dimension. For example, the rise of shopping on the internet, which is in essence a marketing innovation, also required cultural innovation (customers may at first have been sceptical to this selling channel and hence were to become open to this new way of buying goods) and business and supply chain innovations (e.g. a new logistic system to get the products to the consumer) before this selling channel really impacted selling economies at scale³⁸. To put it differently, **actions in different dimensions are needed for achieving impact at scale**^{39,40}. This underlines the importance and

³⁵ King, A., 1979. The club of rome a case study of institutional innovation. *Interdisciplinary Science Reviews*, 4(1): 54–64. <https://doi.org/10.1179/030801879789801722>

³⁶ Drucker, P. (2007). *Innovation and Entrepreneurship*.

³⁷ Roberts, N. (2006). *The Corporation that Changed the World: How the East India Company Shaped the Modern Multinational*, Pluto Press, London.

³⁸ Kamarck, E. (2004). *Government Innovation around the World*. Ash Institute for Democratic Governance and Innovation, John F. Kennedy School of Government, Harvard University, 51. doi:10.2139/ssrn.51766

³⁹ Takey, S. M., & Carvalho, M. M. (2016). Fuzzy front end of systemic innovations: A conceptual framework based on a systematic literature review. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 111: 97–109.

⁴⁰ Midgley, G., & Lindhult, E. (2021). A systems perspective on systemic innovation. *Systems Research and Behavioral Science*, 38(5), 635–670. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sres.2819>

relevance of **taking a systemic approach for appropriately materializing Systemic Innovations**^{41,42,43,44,45}.

Sartas et al. (2020)⁴⁶ refer to this systemic approach by emphasising the multidimensionality of innovations very explicitly: they talk about ‘innovation packages’ to refer to SIs. Concretely, they pose that an **innovation package** (what we call a SI in ZeroW) encompasses one or few **core innovations** and usually several **complementary innovations**. They visualise the core and complementary innovations as staves of a barrel (see Figure 12). The barrel is thus the innovation package, and the size of the barrel (the content/volume it can bare) represents the capacity of the innovation package (SI) to achieve impact at scale. For example, the development of a new drought-tolerant crop should be interpreted as an **innovation package** wherein the biochemical genetic manipulation technique (which implements drought-resistant genes into the target crop) is the main **core innovation**, while one crucial **complementary innovation** would be the development of an effective and efficient supply system that enables the delivery of the new seeds to those farmers who cultivate in very dry areas. In this particular example, it would make no sense to invest more in the core innovation (i.e. biochemical breeding technique) while the seed supply system to the target users (farmers who would benefit from this drought-resistant crop because they cultivate in a dry area) is not working adequately. This ‘waste’ of investment is illustrated by the leaking drops in Figure 12. As long as this seed supply system is not being improved, this complementary innovation acts as a **bottleneck** to successful scale-up.

⁴¹ Geels, F.W., 2002. Technological transitions as evolutionary reconfiguration processes: a multi-level perspective and a case-study. *Research Policy*, 31: 1257–1274

⁴² Leeuwis, C., & Aarts, N. (2011). Rethinking communication in innovation processes: Creating space for change in complex systems. *Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*, 17(1), 21–36. doi:10.1080/1389224X.2011.536344

⁴³ Schut, M., Leeuwis, C., & Thiele, G. (2020). Science of Scaling: Understanding and guiding the scaling of innovation for societal outcomes. *Agricultural Systems*, 184(July), 102908. doi:10.1016/j.agsy.2020.102908

⁴⁴ Smits, R. (2002). Innovation studies in the 21st century: questions from a user’s perspective. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 69: 861–883.

⁴⁵ Wigboldus, S., Klerkx, L., Leeuwis, C., Schut, M., Muilerman, S., & Jochemsen, H. (2016). Systemic perspectives on scaling agricultural innovations. A review. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 36(3). doi:10.1007/s13593-016-0380-z

⁴⁶ Sartas, M., Schut, M., Proietti, C., Thiele, G., & Leeuwis, C. (2020). Scaling Readiness: Science and practice of an approach to enhance impact of research for development. *Agricultural Systems*, 183(August), 102874. doi:10.1016/j.agsy.2020.102874

Fig. 1. Scaling Readiness Barrel to illustrate how innovation(s) with the lowest readiness limit an innovation package's capacity to achieve impact at scale.

Figure 12: The Scaling Readiness Barrel to illustrate how innovation dimension(s) with the lowest readiness limit an innovation package's capacity to achieve impact at scale. Adopted from Sartas et al. (2020).

After the relevant innovation dimensions are identified, it makes sense to keep track of the evolutions of the needed (innovative) actions corresponding to the identified dimensions. Such **simultaneous monitoring** is expected to be challenging, since literature shows that multidimensional approaches to innovation benefit from context-adapted and tailor-made supporting mechanisms and tools, however, how exactly suchlike mechanisms and tools contribute to successful innovation is

complex and ambiguous^{47,48,49,50,51}. Therefore, the **SIRL tool (presented hereafter) was specifically developed with the purpose to support the nine ZeroW SILLs in (1) identifying dimensions wherein some kind of action is needed for reaching impact with their FLW-solution, and (2) coordinating the progression made in those dimensions.** The SIRL tool is inspired by the concepts and measures proposed by Sartas et al. (2020)³⁷, but it is specifically adapted to serve the ZeroW SILLs in their SIP.

5.1.2. What does this mean for ZeroW?

In line with the above, in ZeroW, we pose that the SIs for a zero FLW supply chain, that are developed in the SILLs, each consist of a set of (innovative) actions. Further, we refer to this set by using the term SI. Thus, in ZeroW, when we talk about SI, we refer to what Sartas and colleagues call ‘innovation packages’. **Each innovation or action from the set addresses a different dimension that has some role in resolving the FLW problem of interest in that SILL.** For some dimensions, this role will be very explicit and straightforward. For others dimensions, this role will be less directly linked to the core idea of the FLW-solution, but nevertheless the role of this dimensions may be important for the solution to eventually achieve impact at scale. In this way, each SILL must aim to address as many relevant dimensions as needed to improve the readiness level of the solution (because more dimensions address more leverage points that are crucial to bring about transformative change)^{52,53,54}. Contrary to what has usually been an implicit assumption, we do not necessarily presume that a technological innovation is always the starting point or the core innovation of a FLW solution. Instead, we assume that it is **the combination**

⁴⁷ Cronin, E., Fieldsend, A., Rogge, E., & Block, T. (2022). Multi-actor Horizon 2020 projects in agriculture, forestry and related sectors: A Multi-level Innovation System framework (MINOS) for identifying multi-level system failures. *Agricultural Systems*, 196(December 2021), 103349. doi:10.1016/j.agsy.2021.103349

⁴⁸ Biermann, F., Man-san, C., Aysem, M., Pattberg, P. (2007). *Multi-stakeholder Partnerships for Sustainable Development: Does the Promise Hold?* (No. 1847208665). Edward Elgar Publishing, UK.

⁴⁹ Kilelu, C.W., Klerkx, L., Leeuwis, C. (2013). Unravelling the role of innovation platforms in supporting co-evolution of innovation: contributions and tensions in a smallholder dairy development programme. *Agricultural Systems*, 118, 65–77

⁵⁰ Murray, R., Caulier-Grice, J., & Mulgan, G. (2010). *The Open Book of Social Innovation. Young* (Vol. 30). Retrieved from http://www.addmecop.eu/home/european/library/literature/Social_Innovator_020310.pdf

⁵¹ Sartas, M., Schut, M., Hermans, F., van Asten, P., Leeuwis, C. (2018). Effects of multi-stakeholder platforms on multi-stakeholder innovation networks: implications for research for development interventions targeting innovations at scale. *PLoS One* 13. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0197993>.

⁵² Fischer, J. and Riechers, M. (2019) A leverage points perspective on sustainability, *People and Nature*, 1: 115–120

⁵³ <http://donellameadows.org/archives/leverage-points-places-to-intervene-in-a-system>

⁵⁴ Abson, D. et al. (2017) Leverage points for sustainability transformation, *Ambio*, 46: 30-39.

of innovations and actions in different dimensions of the SI that **determines the success potential** of the FLW solution.

Implementing several innovation dimensions into the SI solution-building in the SILLs, despite being necessary, will create challenges. **In each SILL, a simultaneous development of innovations/actions in multiple dimensions will happen.** This will in fact demand a lot of SILL members, because they may at some points feel overwhelmed by the various dimensions and related innovations/actions that they need to tackle during the SIP. Appropriate coordination of the multiple innovations/actions (that correspond to the dimensions that were designated to be critical) is therefore a prerequisite for achieving uptake and impact at scale. Indeed, **the different innovation dimensions that are important for successful upscaling of the FLW solutions firstly need to be detected correctly, and secondly, the progressions of the individual innovations/actions corresponding to these critical dimensions need to be monitored simultaneously.** The SIRL is designed to support both activities.

In conclusion, the SIRL tool will help the SILLs to reach successful development and implementation of their innovative FLW solutions: the SIRL triggers SILLs to reflect on the envisioned impacts of their solution by urging them to think deeply how they can achieve these impacts by adopting a systems thinking perspective. By **prompting the SILLs to think systemically** during all the phases of the SIP, the SIRL teaches SILLs that the success of their FLW solution depends on **simultaneous tackling of issues in all dimensions** relevant to their specific FLW solution. Such issues can relate to the need to scale-up certain innovations or to scale-down certain practices or processes that are currently the status quo⁵⁵; in order to successfully scale the FLW SI.

5.1.3. Five innovation dimensions relevant for SIs addressing FLW problems

In what follows, we report on **five generic innovation dimensions** that we expect to be important in FLW SI solutions. This should be seen as a starting point, not an exhaustive inventory of all dimensions that could possibly be important in the context of FLW solution-building. Thus, it is a way of classifying innovation dimensions with FLW solution-building pathways in mind. To arrive at this classification, we started from the nine original innovation types from the ZeroW GA (see Table 11 and Figure 13), but we restructured them (some innovation types were

⁵⁵ Wigboldus, S., Klerkx, L., Leeuwis, C., Schut, M., Muilerman, S., & Jochemsen, H. (2016). Systemic perspectives on scaling agricultural innovations. A review. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 36(3). doi:10.1007/s13593-016-0380-z

omitted, some merged, others split up) into five generic dimensions (see Annex 3 for more information).

It should be noted that our proposed classification hereafter is a way of interpreting dimensions that might be altered throughout the ZeroW project, based on SILLs' feedback on what works best for characterizing their SI. Some of the generic dimensions overarch several sub-dimensions that may be relevant to distinguish. This is to create structure for SILLs. But SILLs must, at all times, reflect on what is the most useful way of distinguishing innovation dimensions for their own unique FLW solution. **How many and which innovation dimensions must be addressed in their SI (= their FLW solution) depends on each SILL's specific context.** Importantly, SILL members should decide **together** which innovation dimensions they want to incorporate in their SI FLW solution building.

(1) Technology dimension

The technology innovation dimension captures all technology aspects that play a role in (i) the core idea/concept of the FLW solution; or (ii) 'side activities' that enable the realisation of the solution, with regard to prototyping, testing, and demonstration; or (iii) 'side activities' needed for commercializing and scaling the solution for widespread use; or (iv) more than one of the former. It is about technological aspects that are substantially improved or totally new, which can relate to various fields such as ICT equipment (hardware and software), new ICT technologies (e.g. AI, quantum, blockchains), sensors, new breeding techniques, proteomics, renewable energy.

(2) Behavioural dimension

This innovation dimension comprises all **societal and psychosocial aspects** that affect the development, acceptance, uptake and scaling up of the FLW solution. It is likely that SI can only be reached if the other (central) innovations from the SI are accompanied by one or more actions or changes in the behavioural dimension. These can be changes in **habits, routines and expectations** of (i) employees/managers in companies (e.g. attributing more value to waste avoidance practices as beneficial for corporate image and hence being another type of value-creation for the company but economic profit); (ii) consumers in the supermarket (e.g. not expecting anymore a full assortment availability all day long, buying also the ugly carrots), (iii) consumers in the out-of-home consumption context (e.g., requesting doggy-bags), or (iv) certain household members during in-home food preparation and consumption activities (e.g. using tough parts of vegetables for soup making). Another type of behavioural innovations deal with **cultural changes**,

e.g., openness of consumers for new types of foods (e.g. algae), or e.g., the rise of a collective disapproval of practices that previously were not shameful or 'not-done', such as leaving a massive amount of yield at the field because prices are bad at the moment of harvest time. In a word, behavioural innovations relate in one way or another to e.g. **social norms, expectations, shared values, awareness levels of people, attitudes, education, knowledge and know-how.**

The scope of the behavioural innovation dimension is thus rather broad; and it might be more practical for SILLs to distinguish a couple of sub-dimensions. We expect that the most relevant sub-dimensions in the context of FLW solutions are the **social and cultural innovation dimensions**. However, this does not imply that each of these sub-dimensions will need to be addressed in each SILL. Neither does it imply that these sub-dimensions comprehensively make up the behavioural dimension: it is possible that another sub-dimension will be identified when the SILL is materialized by the ZeroW SILLs in WP5.

In summary, **socio-cultural innovations** seek new approaches for addressing social needs that relate to culture, health, education, and well-being. They relate to new ways of thinking about social systems which lead to added value when applied in practice⁵⁶. If successful, such innovations typically create a (semi-)permanent change in behaviour of the targeted social group. More precisely, socio-cultural innovations deal with the **reorganisation of structures, attitudes, visions, beliefs, behaviours, cultures, soft institutions, networks, and social relationships that are predominant in the context of current food systems**. This can concern, amongst others, prevailing habits, values, norms, expectations, and requirements with regard to food products' quality aspects of various actors from the food system, such as consumers, retailer/restaurant personnel/managers, and food companies.

Some literature distinguishes between *cultural innovations* on the one hand, which relate to values and norms; and *social innovations* on the other hand, which relate to networks, relationships, collaborations, and alliances²⁴. First, **cultural innovations** start from the identification of a cultural issue, which could state that reducing food waste will likely need changes in consumer habits, both in household and out-of-home-consumption contexts. These changes may be reached through a set of solutions, such as nudging interventions and awareness-raising campaigns. For this, first a profound understanding of why, how, and when consumers buy certain foods is needed, so that FLW occurrences can be anticipated and prevented. Second, **social innovations** relate to the creation, renewal or transformation of social

⁵⁶ Mieg, H. A., & Töpfer, K. (Eds.). (2013). Institutional and social innovation for sustainable urban development (Vol. 1). London: Routledge.

relations in the search for new ways of working together to achieve societal goals^{57,58}. To name an example in the context of FLW, new/unusual collaborations that allow unprecedented win-win situations, like partnerships between retail agents and renowned chef cooks or social media influencers, which deliver healthy and anti-FLW meals/food delivery programmes.

Some authors have distinguished three phases of behavioural change. The first phase, referred to as the 'unfreeze' or 'readiness' phase, is about getting parties/stakeholders involved and prepared for the change. The second phase, called the 'change' or 'adoption' phase, comprises the period during which the change is still on trial. The third phase, called 'refreeze' or 'institutionalization', involves all efforts for getting the changes internalised into the organisation/societal group of interest^{59,60,61,62}. SILLs may take these phases into account when moving to step 2 of the SURL, wherein they should decide on the meaning of different readiness levels to be used for expressing the maturity of the solution to the specific issue that they defined in the behavioural dimension during step 1 of the SURL.

It should be noticed that we here take a more constraint interpretation of social innovation compared to many interpretations proposed in the literature. For example, a widely accepted notion of social innovation with a much broader scope is⁶³:

“Social innovations can be understood as new solutions (products, services, models, markets, processes etc.) that simultaneously meet a social need (more efficiently and effectively than existing solutions) and lead to new or improved capabilities, assets and/or relationships. In other words, social innovations are both good for society and enhance society’s capacity to act.”

⁵⁷ Moulart, F., MacCallum, D., Mehmood, A., Hamdouch, A. (2013). General introduction: the return of social innovation as a scientific concept and a social practice. In: Moulart, F., MacCallum, D., Mehmood, A., Hamdouch, A. (Eds.), *The International Handbook on Social Innovation: Collective Action, Social Learning and Transdisciplinary Research*. Edward Elgar, Cheltenham, UK and Northampton, USA, pp. 1–6.

⁵⁸ astro-Arce, K., & Vanclay, F. (2020). Transformative social innovation for sustainable rural development: An analytical framework to assist community-based initiatives. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 74(October 2019): 45–54. doi:10.1016/j.jrurstud.2019.11.010

⁵⁹ Lewin, K. (1947). Frontiers in group dynamics: concept, method and reality in social science; social equilibria and social change. *Human Relations*, (1): 5-41

⁶⁰ Burnes B. (2004). Kurt Lewin and the Planned Approach to Change: A Re-appraisal. *Journal of Management Studies*, 41(6): 977-1002

⁶¹ Armenakis A.A. & Harris S.G. (2002). Crafting a Change Message to Create Transformational Readiness. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 15(2): 169-83.

⁶² Blackman, D., O’Flynn, J., & Ugyel, L. (2013). A Diagnostic Tool for Assessing Organisational Readiness for Complex Change. *Anzam Australia and Newzealand Academy of Management*, 4–6. Retrieved from https://www.anzsog.edu.au/media/upload/publication/131_Flynn-and-Ugyel-Diagnostic-Tool-ANZAM-2013.pdf

⁶³ Davies, A., Mulgan, G., Norman, W., Pulford, L., Patrick, R., Simon, J. (2012). *Systemic Innovation*. Social Innovation Europe.

Whereas the above definition states that products, models, markets, and processes can be considered as being a social innovation, in ZeroW it is presumed that the new solutions developed in the SILLs are SIs, of which the social dimension may be an important part, though it is restricted to the action of the package that realizes the capacity of society to act and/or that concerns the concretisation of the societal/social issue that needs to be resolved for the whole innovation package to be able to generate impact.

To summarize, the aim of the behavioural innovation dimension is to explore whether the society is 'ready' for the FLW solution developed in the SILL; in terms of prevailing beliefs, norms and behaviours; as well as in terms of having sufficient capacity to make use of the FLW solution in a sustainably scaled way. Holt et al (2007, 235)⁶⁴ defined readiness for change as: *"A comprehensive attitude that is influenced simultaneously by the content (i.e., what is being changed), the process (i.e., how the change is being implemented), the context (i.e., circumstances under which the change is occurring), and the individuals (i.e., characteristics of those being asked to change) involved"*.⁵⁴ These are indeed four pillars that SILLs can take into account when evaluating the maturity level of the behavioural dimension in their FLW solution.

(3) Policy and governance dimension

Bruno et al. (2020)⁶⁵ state that "innovations (especially disruptive ones) require legal compliance check to become permanently adopted. No new innovation can survive if going against the existing set of binding rules that govern the selected domain while, at the same time, any legal system evolves over time as a result of breakthrough innovations which urge the need to revise spaces of legitimate action or configuring new spaces so as to enlarge the range of possibilities." Indeed, implementation and scaling up of new innovative FLW solutions might be hindered by obstacles that relate to the legal environment in which the company or industries at stake is/are operating⁶⁶. This underlines the relevance of a **legal/policy innovation dimension**. This sub-dimension contains binding laws, broader legislative frameworks (at local, national, global levels, and various policy domains,

⁶⁴ Holt, D.T., Armenakis, A.A., Field, H.S. & Harris, S.G. (2007). Readiness for Organizational Change: The Systematic Development of a Scale. *The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 43(2): 232-55.

⁶⁵ Bruno, I., Donarelli, A., Marchetti, V., Panni, A. S., Covino, B. V., Lobo, G., & Molinari, F. (2020). Technology readiness revisited: A proposal for extending the scope of impact assessment of European public services. *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series*: 369–380. doi:10.1145/3428502.3428552

⁶⁶ Pitkänen, O., Soininen, A., Laaksonen, P., & Hurmelinna, P. (2002). Legal constraints in Readiness to exploit mobile technologies in B2B. *International Workshop on Wireless Strategy in the Enterprise*, 5. Retrieved from http://128.214.112.31/u/opp/pub/readiness_berkeley.pdf

such as food safety and intellectual property policies), and ethical considerations within the scope of legal compliance.

Governance innovations cover the introduction and/or development of new paradigms to resolve complex social conflicts and find better ways to share limited resources. They aim to achieve better decisions in dynamic systems that are characterised by complexity. This can be achieved by strengthening cooperation across different sectors and among stakeholders. Governance innovations can also relate to changes in power structures, hard institutions and prevailing ideology²⁴.

In summary, this innovation dimension encompasses actions that pave the way for new and innovative policies (if needed for the FLW solution to achieve impact at scale), legal frameworks, and educational programs in support of the transition to a near-zero FLW system.

(4) Business dimension

The business innovation dimension is situated at the level of single companies. (innovative) actions in the business dimensions relate to new or adapted business strategies, organisations and operational practices; either to anticipate or in response to internal and external changes. Concretely, they may concern new, substantially improved, or impactful adaptations in: management strategies, organisational structures, or working practices (routines, departmentalization, training, capacity building) to improve performance and profitability. For example, new waste management and auditing schemes.

We consider three major sub-dimensions: the strategic, organisational, and operational innovation dimensions. The **strategic** innovation dimension contains innovative approaches in marketing, finances (e.g. cash flow management), market and product or service aspects. The **organisational** innovation dimension covers the need for new or adapted infrastructures, roles, processes, and functions. Hence an organisational innovation is a new or substantially improved organisational method or structure in working practices, workplace organisation, and/or external relations in order to improve performance and profitability⁶⁷. The **operational** innovation dimension concerns practical, daily operating aspects, such as manufacturing processes and employee/manager skills needed to implement the innovative solution.

⁶⁷ OECD/Eurostat. (2005). *Oslo Manual: Guidelines for Collecting and Interpreting Innovation Data. The Measurement of Scientific and Technological Activities* (3rd Editio). Paris: OECD Publishing. doi:10.4337/9781786438935.00024

(5) Value chain dimension

The value chain dimension is similar to the business dimension because it also relates to new or substantially improved strategic, organisational, and operational practices. However, the actions and/or innovations identified in this dimension transcend the level of individual businesses. Indeed, for FLW systemic solutions to be implemented in the food supply chain, changes may be needed in the way different food actors collaborate. Such changes will likely alter or affect the process of food transport and value allocation across the food supply chain. For example, new collaborative models that give rise to innovative cross-organisational structures, for example between sectors that were not connected before.

5.2. The use of maturity scales to evaluate the readiness level of an innovation package: from general Innovation Readiness Level to dimension specific Readiness Levels

Only after the SILL members have agreed on what the key innovation dimensions of their SI are, they can start evaluating how 'ready' their FLW solution is with regard to each separate dimension in their SI. In order to do so, SILL members first need to decide what scales they will use for the corresponding innovation dimensions. This can be a scale from the literature (see Annex I) or this can be a self-made scale that is fully custom-made to their SI context. When SILLs decide to make a scale themselves (in case the scales from the literature are not useful to be applied), we advise to use a tool from the toolbox (see ZeroW project's Deliverable 4.2; the SI toolbox) as practical approach to create these scales. We recommend Theory of Systems Change, Fish Bowl, Brainstorm, or Focus Group. Making a scale might be tricky, but **as soon as SILL members manage to precisely define and agree on what exactly should be achieved before reaching the next readiness level for an innovation dimension, it will become more concrete how they can reach their targets, and this will help SILLs to make the right investment decisions for achieving impact with their SI** (in WP6 of ZeroW, we will work further on these investment strategies, departing from the results of the SILL achieved by each SILL).

The readiness level scales that are available in the literature are presented in Annex I; through detailed descriptions of each readiness level of the respective innovation dimension. Most of these descriptions are directly adopted from the original source, however, when adaptations towards the ZeroW context were necessary, it is indicated in the table heading. Still, SILLs should consider these readiness ladders from the Annex I as examples of the level of detail they should reach in describing which achievements are needed for entering a higher level. **SILLs should always adapt**

the ladders according to their unique context and according to the definition of the innovations they had identified and characterized in step 1 of the SIRL.

Below, we provide more background information about these readiness level scales.

5.2.1. General Innovation Readiness Level

Table 3 presents the innovation readiness level scale proposed by Sartas et al. (2020)³⁷ to guide R4D teams in assessing the readiness of non-technological innovations. This is a generic way of defining readiness levels, and hence applicable to various innovation domains. The SILLs can use this scale as a starting point for developing a specific, applied readiness scale that they need. The nine readiness levels can be seen as sublevels of the three main phases in innovation processes proposed Garud et al. (2013):

- Levels 0 – 4 correspond to the invention phase, which comprises the emergence and development of an idea. This phase of the innovation process is also known as the ‘Fuzzy Front End of innovation’ in the literature. Proper management in this phase is crucial for success (Bocken et al., 2014; Stevens, 2014; Koen et al., 2001).
- Levels 5 – 7 cover the actual development of the innovation, i.e., the elaboration, concretisation, materialisation, and realization of the initial innovation idea and concept.
- Levels 8 – 9 encompass the implementation and the widespread acceptance of the innovative solution. Only here, the new innovation is being tested for the first time in uncontrolled environmental conditions.

5.2.2. Technology readiness level

The purpose of the TRL is to assess the maturity of a technological innovation or an individual technology. A TRL number is obtained once the description in Table 4 has been achieved. For example, successfully finalizing TRL 4 (i.e., achieving validation in a controlled environment) does not automatically change the TRL to level 5. Instead, TRL 5 is achieved once there is validation in a relevant environment. The technology remains TRL 4 until the relevant environmental validation is complete (NASA).

Similar to the higher-level distinction made in the previous section for the general innovation readiness levels, the positioning of the technology innovation in the SILLs on the TRL ladder can be facilitated by considering following key differences between three main phases (Bruno et al., 2020):

- TRLs 1-4: initial idea has not yet left laboratory
- TRLs 5-7: usage context comes into play
- TRLs 8-9: fully implemented and tested innovation

5.2.3. Readiness levels for the behavioural innovation dimension

The societal readiness level (Table 5) is the most general readiness ladder, currently available in the literature, that is relevant to the behavioural dimension of FLW systemic innovation. The assessment of whether society is ready to adopt the solution should include the evaluation of the level of current and expected/predicted societal acceptance of a certain innovative technology, product, process, strategy, intervention, etc. (Bruno et al. 2020)⁵⁶. Since the behavioural dimension encompasses social, cultural, and education aspects, as well as soft institutions, the maturity/readiness level of this dimension is influenced by prevailing norms, values, informal rules, beliefs, attitudes, education and extension programmes, and knowledge levels.

SILLs might come to decide that the SRL from the literature (presented in Table 5) alone is too broad for improving their SI in practice. Assessing the readiness to adopt the FLW solution can for example be made more feasible by e.g. focussing on a specific user group in a first stage.

5.2.4. Readiness levels in the policy innovation dimension

Table 6 presents the Legal Readiness Level proposed by Bruno et al. (2020). SILLs may decide to adapt this scale based on the specific issue identified or needed action plan that they have formulated for this dimension in step 1 of the SIRL.

Purpose of LRL

This maturity model looks at the legal and regulatory implications of innovation in terms of compliance, but also transformative power. The goal is to identify legal and regulatory obstacles or gaps that must be solved in order to favour the deployment of new solutions in 'a more innovation prone and individual rights protective environment' (Bruno et al., 2020).

Relevance of LRL

Innovations (especially disruptive ones) require legal compliance check to become permanently adopted. the higher the LRL score, the higher is such compliance level. No new innovation can survive if going against the existing set of binding rules that govern the selected domain while, at the same time, any legal system evolves over time as a result of breakthrough innovations which urge the need to revise spaces of legitimate action or configuring new spaces so as to enlarge the range of possibilities. Thus: need to consider the complex interaction of the innovation system with the legal system, including any pressure to modify the legal system in order to unlock the potential of the new innovative solution (Bruno et al., 2020).

Scope of LRL

- Formal rules
- Legislative frameworks (local, national, global levels; and multiple policy domains)
- governance
- ethical considerations & legal compliance

5.2.5. Readiness levels in the business and value chain innovation dimensions

A) Organisational sub-dimension

Table 7 presents the ORL as proposed by Bruno et al. (2020)⁵⁶. We expect SILLs will be able to very easily adapt this maturity scale towards their specific context of interest, and we expect that it may be useful to use this scale as a starting point both for issues at the business and at the value chain level.

Purposes of ORL

- (1) to identify and carefully describe the innovative solution's major impacts on organisational structures and functions
- (2) to assess the preparedness level of an organisation (can be a single company, or an organisation at the interface between individual companies across the supply chain) receiving a solution (i.e., readiness to implement the new solution in terms of organisation)

Relevance of ORL

Any core innovation (be it technical, social, organisational) requires being embedded in the organisational environment to become permanently adopted. Thus, need for consideration of possible organisational impacts of testing and/or adopting an innovation, leading to e.g. infrastructure, process and/or human skills related requirements. Organisational interoperability is reached when distinct public sector bodies are able to align their business processes, responsibilities and expectations to achieve commonly agreed and mutually beneficial goals (Bruno et al. 2020).

Scope of ORL

ORL is often an ad hoc maturity model related to the organisational impact of a certain technology, product, process, or intervention. Such impact can refer to the necessity of changes in:

- 1) professional roles, competencies and skills (people);
- 2) organisational functions and processes (structures);

3) physical infrastructures (materials & equipment);

4) governance systems

B) Operational sub-dimension

Manufacturing readiness level (see Table 8)

Purpose of ManuRL

to assess the maturity of a given technology, system, subsystem, or component from a manufacturing perspective. MRLs provide decision-makers (at all levels) with a common understanding of the relative maturity (and relating risks) associated with manufacturing technologies, products, and processes.

Relevance of ManuRL

As explained by (Wu et al. 2012)⁶⁸: “the readiness of a technology does not necessarily indicate that the related products are ready to be manufactured in an affordable and operationally effective manner. Technical challenges regarding material availability, system integration and manufacturing process development may continue to hamper the widespread application of the technology.”

Links to other RLs?

The ManuRL is complementary to the TRL methodology since a certain level of technology maturity is a prerequisite to reaching a certain level of manufacturing maturity.

C) Strategy sub-dimension

Marketing readiness level (see Table 10)

Purpose of MarketingRL

To assess the marketing maturity of the new solution.

This maturity ladder can be used for evaluating innovations that encompass some kind of new marketing method; involving significant changes in one or more of the following domains:

- product design and/or packaging,
- product placement,
- product promotion,

⁶⁸ Wu, C., Wang, B., Zhang, C., Wusk, R. A., & Chen, Y. W. (2012). Bioprinting: an assessment based on manufacturing readiness levels. *Critical Reviews in Biotechnology*. doi:10.3109/07388551.2016.1163321

- methods for pricing goods and services.

Scope of marketing innovation dimension:

Often, innovative solutions require innovations in the marketing complex (product/service + its marketing (placement, promotion, pricing)). As such, the marketing innovation dimension can be closely related to or covering the product/service innovation dimension. Product/service innovation occurs when a good or a service is new or significantly improved (i.e.; compared to what was previously offered) with respect to its characteristics or intended use. Such innovation can be created by significant changes in capabilities of existing products or services. This may include significant improvements in technical specifications, components and materials, software in the product, user friendliness or other functional characteristics (OECD/Eurostat 2005). In its most extreme form, it can also concern the creation of a wholly new product/service category. In addition to product innovativeness, the marketing innovation dimension also encompasses new or substantially improved promotion, pricing, placement, packaging or sales strategy to enhance the attractiveness of the product and increase market share.

5.3. Usage of the SIRL tool for determining SI dimensions and measuring SI readiness: towards a practical guide for SILLs

5.3.1. The goals of the ZeroW SIRL assessment tool

The SIRL tool is supposed to prepare the SIs of the SILLs for commercialisation and scaling up. It will be used by all nine ZeroW SILLs in a co-creative and participatory way, meaning that SILLs utilize the tool as a guidance for group discussions on how to embrace the different innovation dimensions that are important in their systemic innovation solution. Only when all relevant dimensions are addressed, the FLW solution will adequately contribute to the transition towards a zero FLW supply chain.

One could state that the SIRL tool ‘formalizes’ the participatory ‘moments of reflection’ that are much needed in interactive innovation processes^{69,70,71,72}. Ideally, the ZeroW SILLs perform these ‘moments of reflection’ on a regular base, so that the monitoring aspect of the SIRL is being materialized. The exact occurrences in time for applying the SIRL tool for each SILL will be determined in the context of monitoring purposes (WP5 - T5.1) and scaling up ambitions (WP6).

The major goals of the SIRL tool are:

1. to foster more in-depth **discussions, collaboration, and co-creation** between SILL members;
2. to **create or improve an interactive and shared understanding** of the FLW problem tackled & solution (in all its dimensionalities) developed in the SILL;
3. to advance SI by encouraging the SILLs to **include and address** as much relevant **SI dimensions** as possible into their FLW solution building. In other words, to prevent them from losing eye on an innovation dimension that appears to be pivotal for developing, implementing, uptake, and scaling up of the FLW solution;
4. to aid the SILLs in **defining the relevant innovation dimensions** that need consideration and development on a maturity ladder to ensure impactful implementation and scaling of their FLW solutions;
5. to enable the SILLs to timely **identify bottlenecks** to their SI;
6. to support the SILLs in **monitoring** their **SI process**, by evaluating the progression for each relevant innovation dimension at different points in time; and by visualizing the progress in each of these innovation dimensions;
7. to **assess** the capacity for achieving **impact** through the ZeroW FLW solutions, by evaluating the *innovation readiness* of all relevant innovation dimensions included in the SILLs’ systemic innovations;
8. To support **scaling** of the FLW solutions by formalizing and structuring the non-linear, systemic innovation process; through regular implementation of

⁶⁹ Klerkx, L., Aarts, N., Leeuwis, C., 2010. Adaptive management in agricultural innovation systems: the interactions between innovation networks and their environment. *Agric. Syst.* 103, 390–400. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2010.03.012>.

⁷⁰ Garud, R., P. Tuertscher, and A. H. Van de Ven. 2013. Perspectives on innovation processes. *Academy of Management Annals* 7(1):775–819.

⁷¹ Knickel, K., G. Brunori, S. Rand, and J. Proost. 2009. Towards a Better Conceptual Framework for Innovation Processes in Agriculture and Rural Development: From Linear Models to Systemic Approaches. *The Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension* 15(2):131–146.

⁷² Van de Ven, A. H. 2017. The innovation journey: you can’t control it, but you can learn to maneuver it. *Innovation: Management, Policy and Practice* 19(1):39–42.

reflective evaluation moments for monitoring progress and adjusting practices if needed.

The following chapters describe the SIRL tool and how it should be used by the SILLs. Section 5.3.2 elaborates the first and crucial step of the SI readiness assessment, namely the exploration of **what innovation dimensions must be included** to turn the FLW solution idea into a real, successful systemic innovation. Section 5.3.3 provides guidance for step 2 of the SI readiness assessment, which is the **evaluation of the readiness levels**. A readiness level should be determined for each (sub-)dimension that was declared important in step 1. The boxes provide prompting questions that can directly be used during the **SIRL workshops**, for which more practical guidance is provided in section 5.3.4.

5.3.2. SIRL step 1: Define the relevant core and complementary innovations of the systemic FLW solution

The first step of the SIRL covers the exploration and decision of what innovation dimensions should be considered in order to increase the success chances of the systemic FLW innovative solution of the SILL. In other words, the first goal of the ZeroW SIRL tool is to support SI by prompting the inclusion of each relevant SI dimension into the FLW solution building. This goal is pursued by encouraging the SILLs to think of any innovation dimension that could possibly be important for the development, uptake and diffusion of their FLW solution, and for realizing impact at scale. The boxes hereafter provide a hands-on guidance for SILLs to perform step 1 of the SIRL; by listing questions that trigger discussions along SILL members about what innovation dimensions to incorporate into their SI.

Box 1: Guiding questions for SILLs to reflect on whether the technology dimension is relevant for their systemic FLW innovation

Overall: discuss with SILL members whether this dimension is important to consider. If so, why? Make use of the questions below to prompt the discussion. Be as specific as possible. Specify/refine/rephrase the scope of the technology dimension, and define sub-dimensions if necessary.

If it remains unclear whether or not there is an issue in this dimension that needs to be tackled, should the SILL take action to further explore this dimensions? For example, by involving or consulting someone with expertise? If yes, discuss what actions to take and who is responsible.

Box 2: Guiding questions for SILLs to reflect on whether the behavioural dimension is relevant for their systemic FLW innovation

Discuss with SILL members whether this dimension is important to consider. If so, why? Make use of the questions below to prompt the discussion. Be as specific as possible. Specify/refine/rephrase the scope of the behavioural dimensions, and define sub-dimensions (e.g. knowledge/socio-cultural/other) if this is considered useful for following-up the SI process in the future.

1. Is the *mindset* (of the public, involved actors, investors, policy makers, end users, etc.) ready for adoption, implementation, diffusion, and scaling of the FLW solution?
2. Are there any issues with regard to *knowledge levels* that might hamper SI development and/or the readiness for adoption, uptake, diffusion, and scaling of the FLW solution?
3. Are there any issues with regard to prevailing (*implicit*) *norms, informal rules, beliefs, values, attitudes, etc.* that might hamper the SI development and/or the readiness for adoption, diffusion, and scaling of the FLW solution?
4. When exploring potential issues in the behavioural domain, ask the question: what is the issue exactly? How exactly is the issue expected to impact the SI process of the SILL? Describe the detected issue as precisely as possible (= this is the starting point of SIRL step 2, since this formulation/description corresponds to either level 1 or 2 of the corresponding RL, depending on the level of detail. Level 1 is the acknowledgement of the existence of an issue; level 2 is the formulation of the issue)
5. Are the detected issues in the behavioural domain limited to a certain *group*, or do they apply to the whole *society*?
6. Do the detected issues apply to the *current* state of affairs, or do they include potential *future* pitfalls?
7. What *obstacles* does the issue cause for the development, implementation, and/or scaling up of the FLW solution?
8. *How severe* is this problem with regard to the development, uptake, and scaling of the solution?
9. How to tackle it? (→ this answer may influence the readiness levels to be used)
10. Is there a need for a behavioural innovation (= e.g., altering consumer behaviours through a new way of nudging, changing visions/beliefs using a new type of communication campaign, etc.) to support the implementation and scaling of the FLW solution?

If it remains unclear whether or not there is an issue in this dimension that needs to be tackled, should the SILL take action to further explore this dimensions? For example, by involving or consulting someone with expertise? If yes, discuss what actions to take and who is responsible.

Box 3: Guiding questions for SILLs to reflect on whether the policy dimension is relevant for their systemic FLW innovation

Overall: In ZeroW, we expect that for many FLW solutions, revisions of or even completely new regulations will be needed before extended use of the solution can be realized. Policy and governance innovations may be new and innovative policies, formal rules, legal frameworks, and educational programs to support the transition to a near-zero FLW system. The SILLs are therefore triggered to carefully think of (1) legal implications of their core solution and (2) what legal aspects could possibly enable or constrain the realization of a scaled use of their FLW solution (or a specific part of it)?

Guidance: Discuss with SILL members whether this dimension is important to consider. If so, why? Be as specific as possible.

The questions below may help to prompt the discussion. Refine the scope from policy to a narrower domain, such as legislation, if better suited.

1. Are there any issues with regard to existing institutions / formal rules / policies / legislative framework / ethical considerations / legal compliances
2. Are there currently any legal / institutional / regulatory barriers to the development / uptake / commercialisation / upscaling of the FLW solution?
3. Any legal compliance check needed?
4. Are there currently any formal rules that might hinder uptake of the FLW solution?
 1. If so, what is the issue exactly? describe the issue as precisely as possible
 2. what obstacles does the cause for the implementation and scaling of the FLW solutions?
 3. How severe is this problem wrt the development, uptake, and scaling of the solution?
 4. How to tackle it? (→ this answer will define your levels)
5. Is there a need for policy innovation (= e.g., a new policy, legal framework, funding program, educational program) to support the implementation and scaling of the FLW solution?

If it remains unclear whether or not there is an issue in the policy dimension that needs to be tackled, should the SILL take action to further explore this dimension? For example, by involving or consulting someone with expertise? If yes, discuss what actions to take and who is responsible.

Box 4: Guiding questions for SILLs to reflect on whether the business dimension is relevant for their systemic FLW innovation

Overall: discuss with SILL members whether this dimension is important to consider. If so, why? Be as specific as possible. Distinguish between relevant sub-dimensions, such as organisational / strategy / marketing / operational / manufacturing / process / other types of issues; depending on what is most appropriate for assessing the readiness of the FLW solution's impact capacity.

Make use of the questions below to prompt the discussion

6. Are existing business-related strategies, organisations, structures, infrastructures, operations, functions, processes, roles, etc. appropriate for allowing implementation, commercialisation and scaling of the FLW solution?
7. Subdomains to consider include: product/service innovation, marketing, market, manufacturing, human capital, employee/managing skills
8. Are there currently any strategic/organisational/structural/operational barriers (at the level of individual businesses) that hinder development, uptake, and/or upscaling of the FLW solution?
9. If so, what is the issue exactly? describe the issue as precisely as possible.
10. What obstacles does the detected issue cause for the implementation and scaling of the FLW solutions?
11. How severe is this problem with regard to the development, uptake, and scaling of the solution?
12. How to tackle it? (→ this answer will define your levels)

If it remains unclear whether or not there is an issue in this dimension that needs to be tackled, should the SILL take action to further explore this dimension? For example, by involving or consulting someone with expertise? If yes, discuss what actions to take and who is responsible.

Box 5: Guiding questions for SILLs to reflect on whether the value chain dimension is relevant for their systemic FLW innovation

Overall: discuss with SILL members whether this dimension is important to consider. If so, why? Be as specific as possible. Make use of the questions below to prompt the discussion. Distinguish between relevant subdomains of issues related to value chain processes' performances and efficiencies; depending on what is most appropriate in the wider context of the FLW solution (think of temporal, spatial, product category context)

13. Are there currently cross-organisational issues and/or processes that (may) hinder development, testing, uptake, and/or upscaling of the FLW solution?
14. If so, what is the issue exactly? describe the issue as precisely as possible
15. what obstacles does it cause for the development, prototyping, implementation and scaling of the FLW solutions?
16. How severe is this problem with regard to the development, prototyping, uptake, commercialisation, and scaling of the solution?
17. How to tackle it? (→ this answer will define your levels)

If it remains unclear whether or not there is an issue in this dimension that needs to be tackled, should the SILL take action to further explore this dimensions? For example, by involving or consulting someone with expertise? If yes, discuss what actions to take and who is responsible.

5.3.3. SIRL step 2: Evaluate Innovation Readiness for each core and complementary innovation

Successful introductions of the FLW innovative solutions in their respective markets will depend on the readiness levels of the different innovations which correspond with the dimensions of relevance. More precisely: the readiness of the overall innovation package is limited by the core or complementary innovation that holds the lowest readiness level. The following sections provide materials that aim to support the SILLs in evaluating the current readiness levels of their core and complementary innovations. Some of the presented readiness level ladders are literally taken from the literature, other ladders present variants that are based on a readiness level framework from the literature but adapted according to the ZeroW context and purpose.

Previous readiness level assessment frameworks have mostly focussed on the technological aspect of the innovation package, the most famous and widely applied framework being the technology readiness level (TRL) ladder invented by NASA

(Parasuraman, 2000; Sauser et al., 2008). However, the implementation success of any new innovation package depends not just on the TRL, but rather on a combination of readiness levels that relate to supply, demand, and governance aspects of the innovative solution (Bruno et al. 2020). The SIRL tool triggers the SILLs to evaluate the readiness of each innovation dimension that was identified as important in the previous step. For the evaluations to happen in a similar way across SILLs, so that readiness levels for innovations dimensions can be compared, and hence opportunities for cross-over learning can be identified, some degree of objectivity in the assessment method should be reached. For this, the use of assessment tools, e.g., readiness maturity scales or readiness level ladder is recommended. In Annex I, some readiness levels that are expected to be relevant for the SILLs to use are presented.

Box 6: Guiding questions for SILLs to determine the readiness levels for each relevant innovation from their FLW innovation package

For each dimension, discuss among the SILL members:

1. Will scales/ladders from the literature be used, and if so, will they be adapted first to fit SILL needs? Is distinguishing between nine readiness levels useful and helpful, or is this too many / too few?
2. How many readiness levels would be appropriate? Are the usual 9 levels handy to work with, or are less/more levels needed?
3. Do the current formulations / descriptions of the levels need more clarification / refinement? Are the scales available in the literature clear / too generic / too specific?
4. Did you decide, for a certain dimension, that it would be best to create a new scale that is custom-made to your needs? If yes, explain why and list needs/actions to take in order to build/formulate these levels.
5. Once there is a decision about which scale and how many levels to be used, use colours or numbers (or a combination) to create a spider web / circle that visualises the state of systemic innovation readiness of your solution

Regarding the need to support the claim of having reached certain current level (using e.g. published scientific evidence): ask the group what kind of supporting material is needed to support this claim. Are such materials easy accessible? Agree on a division of tasks regarding the collection and following-up of the supporting materials that clarify why a certain readiness level has been reached.

5.3.4. Preparation and organisation of SIRL workshops

Practically, a participatory approach that brings in the different perspectives and knowledge (e.g. workshop format) is proposed as the ideal way of putting the SIRL into practice. **SIRL Workshops** are preferably face-to-face meetings with as many SILL members attending as possible. Alternatively, the workshop could be organized online. In that case, we advise using online tools, such as a Miro or MURAL whiteboard, to stimulate a dynamic discussion that includes opinions of every participant. Additionally, it may be good to involve people with specific expertise into the SIRL assessment activities. We advise to consider the use of tools (see D4.2), such as workshop, brainstorm, or tomorrow's headlines to enrich SI discussions that are triggered by the SIRL.

5.4. Future use of the SIRL within ZeroW

5.4.1. Pilot cases on SILL1, SILL4, and SILL2

A preliminary version of the SIRL was voluntarily tried-out by three SILLs. A report on the trial of SILL2 will only be available on 4th of July, hence this feedback could not be integrated yet. The pilot cases from SILL1 and SILL4 revealed that:

- SILLs need practical training and tools so that they are capable of performing the SIRL assessment in a participatory way
- Need for a shared understanding of the SI dimensions. What can help to make the dimensions more comprehensible, in a more concrete and tangible way, is an inventory of diverse FLW-related examples in each innovation dimension. Such an inventory is being set up at the moment of writing. A first version will be available to the SILLs during the F2F meeting on 12-13 July 2022. This inventory will be further supplemented with SILL-examples once the SIRL is being put into practice during WP5.

Because of the above, a very comprehensive and detailed step-by-step practical guide that complements the explanation of the SIRL (presented in the previous sections) will be created. A first version of this practical guide will be presented to the SILLs during the f2f-meeting in July and thereafter it will be refined or adapted based on the try-out performed there, which will indicate the needs of the SILLs.

5.4.2. All SILLs will use the SIRL during ZeroW

On 12-13 July 2022, SILLs will get acquainted with the SIRL during an interactive workshop during the face-to-face meeting. Furthermore, the SIRL will be used by all SILLs in the context of WP5. Results of the SIRL will also be used further out the

ZeroW project, particularly in WP6 where SIRL results will be the starting point for determining strategies that are needed for successful scale-up of the FLW solutions.

Each SILL will use the SIRL to assess all dimensions of the systemic innovations on its readiness level and express concrete readiness progress ambitions and action plans. Such assessment of SILLs will also exhibit their system completeness to identify which Scaling Readiness (innovation) dimensions are the most relevant measures of success and how to improve the SIRL, paving the way for systemic innovation commercialisation. As such, the SIRL will be used during the entire duration of the innovation process, as a monitoring tool, to continuously steer innovation evolution.

6. Conclusion

The ZeroW project has the ambition to transform the food supply chain towards a zero FLW supply chain by 2050. This impact will be achieved by the FLW solution of the SILLs that are built during the ZeroW project, and should be taken up at large scale after the project. To really reach transformation, a systemic approach is needed. This means that (i) the FLW solutions themselves need to be systemic, for which the SIRL (chapter 5) mainly helps the SILLs; and (ii) the process of building the FLW solutions (through phases of preparation, set-up, prototyping, testing, assessment, demonstration) must be systemic, meaning that the process happens in a participatory way in which definitions, interpretations and understandings of FLW must be shared across the SILLs networks. This deliverable supports the latter by providing a FLW definition for ZeroW, a better view on conflict mechanisms between FLW solutions and food poverty problems, and the SIRL, which is a tool that will be used by the SILLs (in WP5 context) to reach SI.

When SILLs are building their FLW solutions, it is important that they try to widen the scope of their original innovation idea by including other dimensions in order to reach SI. Supporting the SILLs (being a multi-actor community, who need to work together fruitfully in order to mover their FLW idea into a commercialized SI) in this systemic thinking process is exactly the purpose of the SIRL. The SIRL tool is be based on the Scaling Readiness as proposed by Sartas et al. (2020)³⁷. Its approach not only assesses the maturity of technological innovations, but also of other innovation dimensions (including behavioural and business maturity aspects). As such, the SIRL enables a significant broadening of scope when compared to technological

readiness. The SIRL proposes five main innovation dimensions for which SILLs should consider whether there is a relevant aspect to include into their FLW solution. First, the behavioural dimension contains cultural innovations, which are related to values and norms; and social innovations, which are related to relationships, networks and alliances. Second, the policy dimension considers innovations that are related to power, governance, institutions, ideology and formal laws. Third, innovations in the business dimension relate to new ways of organisational, strategic, and operational structures and management. Fourth, the value chain dimension poses the question whether there is a need for new cross-organisational alliances in the supply chain. Last, technological innovations relate to new or substantially improved technologies and technical improvements. SILLs must not necessarily adhere to or limit themselves to these five generic dimensions when characterizing their FLW SI. Instead, they should be inspired by these dimensions to describe their own unique SI in a detailed and comprehensive way. After SILL partners agree on the dimensions of their SI, they can start evaluating current readiness levels for each innovation dimension. In this way, the SIRL helps them to get insight how far they are with their SI. SILLs will use the SIRL in WP5 to characterize their SI and to evaluate the readiness of their FLW solution. Later, this will be the starting point for building strategies for scale-up in WP6.

7. Annex I: Innovation Readiness Levels from the literature

Table 3: Generic IRLs, their respective basic descriptions, and the type of science and evidence that is needed to support a readiness level claim (source: Sartas et al., 2020).

IRLs	Description	Type of science	Type of evidence
0 Idea	Genesis of the innovation. Formulating an idea that an innovation can meet specific goal	None	None
1 Hypothesis	Conceptual validation of the idea that an innovation can meet specific goals and development of a hypothesis about the initial idea	Conceptual	Generic
2 Basic Model (unproven)	Researching the hypothesis that the innovation can meet specific goals using existing basic science evidence	Conceptual	Generic
3 Basic Model (proven)	Validation of the principles that the innovation can meet specific goals using existing basic science evidence	Basic science	Generic
4 Application Model (unproven)	Researching the capacity of the innovation to meet specific goals using existing applied science evidence	Basic science	Generic
5 Application Model (proven)	Validation of the capacity of the innovation to meet specific goals using existing applied science evidence	Applied science	Generic
6 Application (unproven)	Testing of the capacity of the innovation to meet specific goals within a controlled environment that reflects the specific spatial-temporal context in which the innovation is to contribute to achieving impact	Applied science	Generic
7 Application (proven)	Validation of the capacity of the innovation to meet specific goals within a controlled environment that reflects the specific spatial-temporal context in which the innovation is to contribute to achieving impact.	Applied science (controlled)	Specific to intervention context
8 Incubation	Testing of the capacity of the innovation to meet specific goals in natural/real/uncontrolled conditions in the specific spatial-temporal context in which the innovation is to contribute to achieving impact with support from an R4D	Applied science	Specific to intervention context
9 Ready	Validation of the capacity of the innovation to meet specific goals in natural/real/uncontrolled conditions in the specific spatial-temporal context in which the innovation is to contribute to achieving impact with support from an R4D	Applied science (uncontrolled)	Specific to intervention context

Table 4: Technology Readiness Level (TRL) index used in Horizon 2020 and ERDF (source: NASA)

5-level scale	TRL	Clarification
market launch	TRL9 - Actual system proven in operational environment	System ready for full scale deployment technology has been proven during a successful "mission"
pre-market launch	TRL8 - System complete and qualified	System incorporated in commercial design technology has been tested and "qualified"; it is now ready for implementation into an already existing (technology) system
Final stage of prototyping	TRL7 - System prototype demonstration in operational environment	The working model or prototype has been demonstrated in a real/uncontrolled/natural environment
Validation and demonstration phases	TRL6 - Demonstration of technology in relevant environment	A TRL 6 technology has a <i>fully functional prototype</i> or representational model
	TRL5 - Validation of technology in relevant environment	Simulations are performed in environments that are as close to realistic as possible TRL 5 is a continuation of TRL 4, however, a technology that is at 5 is identified as a breadboard technology and must undergo more rigorous testing than technology that is only at TRL 4
	TRL4 - Validation of technology in laboratory	Laboratory testing of prototype component or process Once the proof-of-concept technology is ready, the technology advances to TRL 4. During TRL 4, multiple component pieces are tested with one another in a <i>controlled environment</i> a proof-of-concept model is constructed
initial stages of R&D project: proof-of-concept is formulated and gradually refined	TRL3 - Experimental proof of concept established	When active research and design begin, a technology is elevated to TRL 3. Generally both analytical and laboratory studies are required at this level to see if a technology is viable and ready to proceed further through the development process.
	TRL2 - Technology concept and/or application formulated	TRL 2 occurs once the basic principles have been studied and <i>practical applications can be applied</i> to those initial findings. TRL 2 technology is very speculative, as there is little to no experimental proof of concept for the technology
	TRL1 - Basic principles are observed	Scientific research is beginning and those results are being translated into future research and development

Table 5: Societal Readiness Level ladder; based on the societal readiness levels (SRL) proposed by Bruno et al. (2020); originally inspired by the Innovation Fund Denmark (2018)

5-level scale	9-level scale
market launch	SRL9 - Actual solution <u>proven in relevant societal environments</u> after launch on the market; the society is using the solution available on the market
pre-market launch	SRL8 - <u>Targeted solution</u> , as well as a plan for societal adaptation, <u>complete and qualified</u> ; society is ready to adopt the solution and have used similar solutions on the market
Final stage of prototyping of the complete solution	SRL7 - <u>Refinement</u> of the solution and, if needed, <u>retesting in real world environments</u> with relevant stakeholders: the society is completely aware of the solution's benefits, a part of the society starts to adopt similar solutions
More and more extended inclusion of societal stakeholders (such as prospective users or other similar groups) in the testing, validation and demonstration phases of the R&D outputs	SRL6 - Solution <u>demonstrated in real world environments</u> and in co-operation with relevant stakeholders to gain feedback on potential impacts: the society knows the solution or similar initiatives and awareness of their benefits increases SRL5 - Solution <u>validated through pilot testing in real or realistic environments</u> and by relevant stakeholders: the society knows the solution or similar initiatives but is not aware of their benefits SRL4 - Solution <u>validated through pilot testing in controlled environments</u> to substantiate proposed impacts and societal readiness: a limited group of the society tests the solution or similar initiatives
Growing awareness of a R&D team about the existence of a societal readiness issue	SRL3 - <u>Initial sharing</u> of the proposed solution with relevant stakeholders (e.g. through visual mock-ups): a limited group of the society knows the solution or similar initiatives SRL2 - Formulation of proposed solution concept and potential impacts; <u>appraisal of societal readiness issues</u> ; identification of relevant stakeholders for the development of the solution SRL1 - <u>Identification</u> of the <u>generic societal need</u> and associated readiness aspects

Table 6: Legal readiness level index (adopted from Bruno et al. 2020)

5-level scale	9-level scale
market launch	LRL9 - solution proven legally and ethically compliant after launch on the market
pre-market launch	LRL8 - Targeted solution, as well as a legal and ethical compliance audit, complete, qualified and ready to be launched on the market
Final stage of prototyping of the complete solution	LRL7 - Refinement of the solution within the existing legal and ethical system and, if needed, proposals for required or recommended changes to some aspects of it
More and more extended consideration of laws, regulations, ethical principles and organisational rules in the testing, validation and demonstration of the targeted solution.	LRL6 - Detailed description of the required or recommended changes in relevant laws, regulations or organisational rules to ensure full compliance with the proposed solution
	LRL5 - Definition of the proposed solution's legal and ethical compliance status after pilot testing in real or realistic organisational environments
	LRL4 - Solution's legal and ethical compliance prospects validated against any required or recommended changes in the legal and/or regulatory system
	LRL3 - Abstract description of the proposed solution's legal and ethical compliance
Growing awareness of a R&D team about the existence of a legal and/or ethical compliance readiness issue	LRL2 - Formulation of the need to enhance the legal normative, laws, rules and guidelines and solution concept; appraisal of legal and ethical compliance issues
	LRL1 - Generic consideration of legal and ethical compliance aspects are observed but nothing has yet been done for the development of the solution

Table 7: Organisational readiness level scale (adopted from Bruno et al. 2020)

5-level scale	9-level scale
market launch	ORL9 - Actual solution proven in relevant organisational environments: roles, processes, functions and infrastructures are correctly used for the solution on the market
pre-market launch	ORL8 - Targeted solution, as well as a plan for organisational embedment, complete and qualified: roles, processes, functions and infrastructures are available
Final stage of prototyping of the complete solution	ORL7 - Refinement of the roles, processes, functions and infrastructures required and retesting of the solution in relevant organisational environments
More and more extended consideration of roles, processes, functions, structures, and governance systems in the phases of testing, validation and demonstration of the targeted outputs	ORL6 - Solution demonstrated in real world environments and in co-operation with relevant stakeholders to gain feedback in order to improve roles, processes, functions and infrastructures required
	ORL5 - Proposed solution validated through pilot testing in real or realistic organisational environments: the organisation which is developing the solution achieves roles, competences and skills, physical infrastructures required
	ORL4 - Solution validated through simulation of major induced changes to substantiate proposed impacts and organisational readiness: the organisation which is developing the solution starts to acquire roles, competences and skills, physical infrastructures required
Growing awareness of a research team about the existence of an organisational readiness issue	ORL3 - Comprehensive description of proposed solution's impacts within the organisation in terms of roles, competences and skills, physical infrastructures
	ORL2 - Formulation of proposed solution concept and potential impacts; appraisal of organisational readiness issues; identification of relevant roles, processes, functions and structures for the solution
	ORL1 - Identification of the organizational need (infrastructures, capabilities, skills) and associated organisational readiness aspects

Table 8: Manufacturing Readiness Level ladder (adopted from OSD Manufacturing Technology Program (2012) Source

9-level scale	Description
MRL9 - Full Rate Production demonstrated and lean production practices in place	Technologies should have matured to TRL 9. This level of manufacturing is normally associated with the Production or Sustainment phases of the acquisition life cycle. Engineering/design changes are few and generally limited to quality and cost improvements. System, components or items are in full-rate production and meet all engineering, performance, quality and reliability requirements. Manufacturing process capability is at the appropriate quality level.
MRL8 - Low rate production demonstrated; Capability in place to begin Full Rate Production	The system, component, or item has been previously produced, is in production, or has successfully achieved low-rate initial production (LRIP). Technologies should have matured to TRL 9. This level of readiness is normally associated with readiness for entry into Full-Rate Production (FRP). All systems engineering/design requirements should have been met such that there are minimal system changes.
MRL7 - Pilot line capability demonstrated; Ready to begin Low Rate Initial Production	The system, component or item has been previously produced, is in production, or has successfully achieved low rate initial production. Technologies should have matured to TRL 9. This level of readiness is normally associated with readiness for entry into Full Rate Production (FRP). All systems engineering/design requirements should have been met such that there are minimal system changes. Major system design features are stable and have been proven in test and evaluation.
MRL6 - Capability to produce systems, subsystems, or components in a production representative environment	System detailed design activity is nearing completion. Material specifications have been approved and materials are available to meet the planned pilot line build schedule. Manufacturing processes and procedures have been demonstrated in a production representative environment. Detailed trade studies are completed and enhancements and risk assessments are underway. Technologies should be on a path to achieve TRL 7.
MRL5 - Capability to produce a prototype system or subsystem in a production relevant environment	This MRL is associated with readiness for a Milestone B decision to initiate an acquisition program by entering into the EMD Phase of acquisition. Technologies should have matured to at least TRL 6. The majority of manufacturing processes have been defined and characterized, but there are still significant engineering and/or design changes in the system itself.
MRL4 - Capability to produce prototype components in a production relevant environment	Identification of enabling/critical technologies and components is complete. Prototype materials, tooling, and test equipment, as well as personnel skills have been demonstrated on components in a production-relevant environment, but many manufacturing processes and procedures are still in development.
MRL3 - Capability to produce the technology in a laboratory environment	This level of readiness acts as an exit criterion for the MSA Phase approaching a Milestone A decision. Technologies should have matured to at least TRL 4. This level indicates that the technologies are ready for the Technology Development Phase of acquisition. Producibility assessments of design concepts have been completed. Key design performance parameters have been identified as well as any special tooling, facilities, material handling and skills required.
MRL2 - Manufacturing Proof of Concept Developed	This level begins the validation of the manufacturing concepts through analytical or laboratory experiments. Experimental hardware models have been developed in a laboratory environment that may possess limited functionality.
MRL1 - Manufacturing Concepts Identified	This level is characterized by describing the application of new manufacturing concepts. Applied research translates basic research into solutions for broadly defined needs.

Table 9: Market Readiness Levels (Source: The OW2 Market Readiness Levels. Available at: OW2 - Introducing the OW2 Project Market Readiness Levels (consulted 2/05/2022))

9-level scale

MRL 9 - Significant market share and global customer base. Properly financed and organized business support. Global active community.

MRL 8 - Customer base of mainstream users. Appropriate financing. Active community support and contributions. Recognized software

MRL 7 - Established product. Customer base of early and mainstream users. Stable financing. Open to community support and contributions.

MRL 6 - Proven product. Customer base of early users. Project fit for third party contributions. Implicit community governance

MRL 5 - Some customers, recent market opening, Core team of developers, untested open source governance

MRL 4 - Several users, project leadership well established

MRL 3 - One declared user (can be internal) with declared project leader

MRL 2 - Basic R&D code developed with one demonstrated use case, some documentation

MRL 1 - Basic R&D code developed

Table 10: Marketing Readiness Level ladder, own adaptation based on Muradovich (2017)

9-level scale	
MRL 9 - MARKET LAUNCH: Distribution and product sale in the open market is organized	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At the final innovation marketing readiness level, a full-scale program on establishment of channels of distribution, promotion and product sale in different markets is organized. Successful cooperation and collaboration with key customers is set. - This level is considered complete after agreement and approval of obtained commercial rates on the basis of stable positive sales dynamics.
MRL 8 - Test marketing is completed and readiness to enter the various sales markets is <u>demonstrated</u>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The efficiency of the solution is confirmed and new production can guarantee the expansion of markets. <p>End of this level = capability to transition to full production and distribution. This level is considered complete if first commercial sales are successful and first profit is gained. There is possibility for transitioning to full production and distribution (there is a product and profit).</p>
MRL 7 - priority plan for sales market development is made	<p>1) Prototype is ready for first reproduction round</p> <p>2) Yet in advance of the release and full-scale sales, some last actions are taken, among which:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using information from the previous level(s), a marketing plan of the priority markets, promotional activities and test sales organization is made. For this, additional information is obtained about: the product's or service's marketing and distribution channels, special aspects of advertising and promotion, surrounding environment, etc. - a good practice is to organize the product/service test marketing in order to clarify whether additional activities for reducing risks and costs are needed. Test marketing provides insight into the potential of the experimental line. - evaluation and analysis of preliminary indicators may reveal problems relating to commercialization of the solution. Dealing with such problems can be supported by a special committee. - Sales department shall be formed and active re-training of personnel involved shall be carried out. After-sales services, customer service, support service and innovation technical support services shall be organized. <p>End of this level = Capability to support limited production; full business team in place. There is an ability to keep a limited production company team fully staffed (there is product and limited profit). The solution can be launched in a limited size.</p>
MRL 6 - Prototype revision and the second phase of prototype testing by the customers is finished	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A prototype of the system is tested in the right environment. A full business plan is ready, covering marketing, management, technological and financial aspects. However, the business/sales team is still not staffed adequately and the solution is not yet ready for commercialisation. - The main purpose of this phase is an approval of the solution by potential customers/users/consumers. This requires: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) thorough revision of the optimal product/service/solution/innovation design and its marketing plan (3 other P's) is carried out considering results obtained at the previous level and the problems identified. 2) then, a second phase of testing of the modified prototype is carried out: the sample/pilot/prototype is demonstrated to the consumers, who provide feedback once again <p>End of this level = capability to support development and design with a market-driven business team. There is a product ready for large-scale production and a marketing plan, but no profit yet</p>

MRL 5 - The first phase of prototype testing is carried out (preferably by the customers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - at this marketing readiness level it is advisable to interact for the first time with customers/end users/distributors/other relevant actors; if involving them as integral participants to the process of innovation is relevant. - first prototype (sample) tested - if possible by a consumers test group (consumers participate in the analysis of test results) - The marketing plan is already realistic, but needs to be confirmed taking into account the characteristics of the final product - if necessary, revision of the optimal product/service/solution/innovation design
End of this level = capability to support project engineering development and design	
MRL 4 - Prototype development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Key technologies and business components are developed and checked for compatibility - First marketing plan (product, placement, promotion, and pricing) ready - a prototype design is completed and a sample produced (product) - if necessary, revision of the optimal product/service/solution/innovation design
End of this level = capability to work limited-scope programs with project teams	
MRL3 - BASIC MODEL (proven): Pre-planning of production volume is completed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Experimental confirmation of commercial prospects: active research and development begins, including theoretical laboratory studies to confirm design features in the market, level of competitiveness and technological solutions - defining and deciding the design of the future product/service/process/innovation/solution/... - exploration of relationships between proposed designs and other innovation dimensions (to timely detect potential mismatches) - A preliminary assessment of the volume of future sales and potential profit is carried out. - the consequence of this level is the final presentation, approval and selection of the optimal product/service/solution/innovation design to be prototyped
End of this level = experimental evidence of business opportunity	
MRL 2 - BASIC MODEL (unproven): main features of the product and marketing method are preliminary decided	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The initial idea is now analysed through a commercial perspective - Performance of a deeper and more thorough study of the solution's key features that are important for ultimately meeting the wishes and requirements of potential consumers and customers. - Such study results in a more concrete idea about future product/solution architecture
MRL 1 - IDEATION & HYPOTHESIS: The concept of the projected product/service/solution/innovation is studied	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - This stage of marketing maturity is the ideation of a new product/service/solution. - The concepts of such future product are explored in order to choose the most optimal variant of the solution. - Identification of a clear service/product demand, need, gap or problem through a needs and gaps analysis (the problem should be either quantifiable or qualitatively explained) - Conducting market research is likely necessary in order to obtain a view on the state of market environment. <p>At the end of this level, the proposed concept (or few selected forms) of the innovative product/service shall be approved (because only after the product concept is approved, drawing up a plan for further development and commercialization is possible).</p>

8. Annex II: Methodological note on the SI dimensions presented in section 5.1.3.

Originally, nine possible dimensions were identified as constituting a comprehensive portfolio for systemic innovation. These dimensions were reported in the GA, see Table 11 and Figure 13. In the context of Task 4.1, these dimensions were re-evaluated based on (1) their relevance for the FLW solutions ideated and materialized in the SILLs; and (2) their capacity to support the SILLs in their SI process in a really helpful, stimulating, comprehensive, straightforward, and unambiguous way. This initial re-evaluation of dimensions of SI made use of (1) consulting relevant literature on SIPs, multi-dimensionality of innovations, and also some specific literature on applied frameworks and tools for supporting innovation processes in various domains; and (2) a pilot exercise for which three SILLs volunteered. Hence the SIRL has been tested independently by SILLs 1, 2 and 4 in order to review the original nine innovation dimensions in terms of practical utility and relevance for the FLW SI solutions which are specific to each SILL. The results of this pilot exercise are reported in section 5.4.1. These two activities (desk research and SIRL piloting workshops) resulted in a classification of innovation dimensions that deviates from the wheel of the GA (Figure 13). This new classification is reported in section 5.1.3 of this deliverable.

We view this classification as an initial revision of the original nine dimensions; since it is performed during the first six months of the ZeroW project, and we do not exclude that more revision rounds may happen, particularly when the SIRL is being used by the SILLs in WP5. The SIRL usage itself will clarify what classification of innovation types into what dimensions works best for SILLs. To put it more concrete, the process of re-evaluation of the innovation dimensions, that has been kick-started in T4.1, is not ought to be finalized with this deliverable; as ZeroW intends the SIRL tool to be an iterative process wherein the following actions recur (not necessarily in the order of the actions listed hereafter): (a) considering SILLs needs and scopes, (b) literature reviewing, (c) evaluating the SIRL's supportive role in the SILL's SIPs, (d) updating the latest SIRL version, and (e) consulting experts. Building the SIRL by use of these actions goes on until the SIRL tool is sufficiently able to support the complex multidimensionality of the systemic innovations created in the SILLs. In particular, this process of repetitive/iterative reflection will be continued in the context of WP5.

Table 11: Preliminary definitions and examples of systemic innovation dimensions, as proposed in the ZeroW GA.

Socio-cultural innovation	Reorganisation of structures, attitudes, behaviours and cultures that lie at the basis of current food systems (habits, values, norms, aesthetic expectations, etc.). For example, a set of creative solutions that anticipate on why and how consumers buy food, to reach a change in habits.
Institutional innovation:	New and innovative policies, legal frameworks, and educational programs to support the transition to a near-zero FLW system.
Governance innovation:	New paradigms to resolve social conflicts and find better ways to share limited resources, by strengthening cooperation across different sectors and among stakeholders. In a word, to achieve better decisions in an era characterised by complexity and a holistic understanding of well-being.
Process innovation:	New and innovative processes that create less waste during the entire chain and thus focus on more efficient use of resources
Organisational innovation:	New or substantially improved management strategies, (cross)organisational structures or working practices (routines, departmentalization, training, capacity building) to improve performance and profitability. For example, waste management and auditing schemes.
Strategy innovation:	New ways to dynamically and constantly adapt business strategies to never ending internal and external changes. Applies to single organisations, collaborative business models and sectors.
Marketing innovation:	New or substantially improved promotion, pricing, placement, packaging or sales strategy to enhance the attractiveness of the product and increase market share for low-waste products. Applies to single organisations and sectors. For example, produce alignment to 'cosmetic standards' during pre-harvest, to initiate alternative marketing channels avoiding food loss
Product innovation:	New or substantially improved goods, wholly new product categories, or services into a business, with respect to its characteristics or intended use, compared to what was previously offered. For example, products based on waste materials.
Technological innovation:	New or substantially improved technology, including equipment, hardware and software and new technologies (e.g. AI, quantum, blockchains). E.g. software reading freshness colour changes and transforming that colour change in remaining shelf life and a product quality score.

Figure 13: The possible dimensions of a systemic innovation; as proposed in the ZeroW GA.